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FACULTY OF ARTS AND SCIENCES

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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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KEYNOTE PRESENTATIONS

2nd KOCAELİ SCIENCE CONGRESS (KOSC-2025)

Kocaeli University, Faculty of Arts and Sciences
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Hydrogen embrittlement in high-strength low-alloy steels

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Abstract

Hydrogen embrittlement has been the cause of failures in high-strength constructional steels used in many industry branches, e.g. shipbuilding and offshore, aircraft and car industry.

Corrosion of marine constructions is prevented by coatings and cathodic protection. The later may be harmful for steels resulting in their hydrogen embrittlement. Steel could be charged with hydrogen in the vicinity of polarisation anode (over-protection), and by presence of some sulfate-reducing bacteria (SRB) in sea-water. Additionally, welded joints contain some amount of hydrogen introduced into a material during welding. This could increase a risk of hydrogen degradation during service.

The aim of the paper is to evaluate susceptibility to hydrogen embrittlement in high-strength low-alloy steel and its welded joints.

A quenched and tempered plate 12 mm in thickness made of S690Q steel grade with submerged arc welded (SAW) and shielded metal arc welded (SMAW) joints were used for investigations. Electrochemical permeation test was performed to evaluate hydrogen uptake and diffusion.

Susceptibility to hydrogen embrittlement of steel and welded joints has been evaluated using monotonically increasing load. Slow strain rate test (SSRT) was carried out on round smooth specimens in air, and seawater under cathodic polarization. Elongation and reduction in area were chosen as measures of susceptibility to hydrogen embrittlement. Fractographic examinations with the use of scanning electron microscope (SEM) were performed to establish mechanisms of hydrogen-enhanced cracking.

High-strength low-alloy steels and its welded joints are susceptible to hydrogen embrittlement when evaluated with the use of SSRT under cathodic polarization. The loss of plasticity is higher for welded joints than for the base metal. However, tested S690Q steel and its welded joints could be safely utilized in marine constructions under cathodic protection provided that overprotection and severe hydrogen charging does not take place.

Keywords: High-strength low-alloy steels; Welded joints; Marine constructions; Hydrogen embrittlement.

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Extensions of Bullen-Type Inequalities using Second Derivative Methods

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Abstract

In this paper, we present a different approach that combines direct integration methods with comparative second derivative techniques. This method allows us to obtain new Hadamard-type inequalities for two functions g and h , where the ratio of their second derivatives is bounded. Our approach not only recovers the existing results of Sarikaya as special cases but also leads to sharper and more general inequalities.

Keywords: Bullen-type inequalities; Second derivative methods.

ORAL PRESENTATIONS

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Stochastic Optimization, Estimation and Prediction via Sieves Method

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Abstract

This abstract presents a comprehensive study of sieve estimators for Functional Autoregressive Processes when the parameter belongs to the space of Hilbert-Schmidt operators. We investigate the fundamental properties of a new class of operators and establish theoretical results that extend previous work in the field. Our main contributions are: (1) the statement of sieve estimator formulas for this new class of operators, (2) the proof of their almost sure and almost complete convergence, and (3) applications to real data prediction, including comparisons with other existing prediction methods on functional data sets, where our approach exhibits competitive results.

The methodology employs advanced techniques from parametric estimation, including the sieves method. We assume that the observed data are functional, belonging to the space of square-integrable functions $L^2[0,1]$, and that they can be modeled by the following autoregressive relation:

$$Y_n(t) = \rho(Y_{n-1})(t) + \varepsilon_n(t). \quad t \in [0,1]$$

where $(\varepsilon_n(t). t \in [0,1])$ is a strong Gaussian white noise in the Hilbert space H , with zero mean and covariance operator C_ε . This implies that $\forall n, k \geq 1, \langle \varepsilon_n, e_k \rangle$ is a Gaussian random variable with zero mean and variance σ_k^2 , with $(e_k, k \geq 1)$ is the basis of $L^2[0,1]$ consisting of the eigenfunctions of the operator C_ε . this notation \langle, \rangle designs the inner product. The parameter ρ is an Hilbert-Schmidt operator.

A sieve denoted by S_k , is a family of parametric subsets of H , indexed by k , which is called the dimension of the sieve. Grenander's approach is based on maximizing the likelihood over the subsets S_k , which are finite-dimensional, in such a way that a local maximum of the likelihood exists. On the other hand, when the dimension of S_k increases with the sample size, the goal is to obtain the convergence of the local maximum likelihood estimator over S_k to the true value of the parameter.

Keywords: Functional autoregressive process; Sieves method; Prediction.

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HOG and Deep Learning-Based Methods for Vendor and Level Classification from Small-Scale Smartphone Images

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Abstract

Here we propose an image-based classification approach that uses HOG for feature representation and CNN-based models for smartphone manufacturers and hardware levels classification from small-scale images. The proposed framework attempts to model device-specific fine-grained visual variations caused by device-specific hardware configurations and manufacturer-specific design attributes. HOG was used for the detection of strong, low-level gradient-based features that were then used as inputs to deep learning models for classification. Our research suggests that the detected HOG features greatly improve the model's ability for visually similar class discrimination, especially when combined with the hierarchical learning capability of CNNs. The model achieved an exceptionally high rate of classification of 99.99%, which demonstrates it effective in distinguishing differences between different device classes. Overlaps between the distributions of features of certain classes, however, suggest a need for additional tuning to improve inter-class discrimination and classification robustness. This suggests the use of traditional feature extraction techniques combined with deep-learning-facilitated classifiers in high-accuracy demanding applications and highly sensitive to minimal visual differences. Future research directions may involve improving generalization through cutting-edge data augmentation, multi-scale learning representations, and adaptive attentions. Dual model has the potential to be applied in mobile device authentication, hardware verification, and digital forensics, particularly in cases where high-resolution images are unavailable or of low quality. The results demonstrate that the combination of hand-crafted features with deep models offers a feasible and effective solution to achieving stable performance in complex classification tasks with implicit visual distinctions.

Keywords: Classification; Features; HOG; Smartphone; Vendor.

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Integral Inequalities via the Multiplicative Absolute Value

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Abstract

This work highlights the role of the multiplicative absolute value in extending classical integral inequalities to the setting of multiplicative calculus.

By employing this concept, we derive new trapezoid and midpoint inequalities for positive and $*$ -differentiable functions such that multiplicative absolute value of the $*$ -derivative is $*$ -convex.

The approach, based on the identity $|\exp \{A\}|_* = \exp |A|$, provides a coherent framework linking additive and multiplicative analysis

Keywords: Trapezoid inequality; Midpoint inequality; Multiplicative fractional integrals; Multiplicative absolute value; Multiplicative convex functions.

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A Study on the Newton-Cotes Quadrature Formula Involving h-convex Functions

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Abstract

The current work presents new estimates on the Newton-Cotes quadrature formula. First, we prove a novel integral identity using functions that are three times differentiable according to the Riemann integral. Further inequality rules may be derived by using the absolute value and assuming that the functions are h-convex. We also show the findings for s-convex functions and P-functions.

Keywords: Newton inequality; h-convex function; Riemann integral.

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On Multiplicative Fractional Calculus

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Abstract

In this talk, we explore the foundations of multiplicative calculus and extend its framework to the fractional setting. Multiplicative calculus replaces the standard additive operations of classical calculus with multiplicative ones, leading to a natural logarithmic-exponential structure that proves particularly useful in modeling phenomena with exponential growth or decay, scale invariance, or relative changes. After briefly reviewing the basic principles of multiplicative differentiation and integration, we introduce and analyze fractional counterparts of classical integral operators, such as the Riemann–Liouville, Hadamard, and Katugampola fractional integrals within the multiplicative paradigm. We discuss their definitions, fundamental properties, and connections to the classical theory via logarithmic transformations. The presentation aims to highlight both the theoretical coherence of fractional multiplicative calculus and its potential applications in areas where multiplicative dynamics are inherent, including certain problems in economics, biology, and signal processing.

Keywords: Multiplicative calculus; Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals; Hadamard fractional integrals; Katugampola fractional integrals.

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Automorphisms of Free Metabelian Lie Algebras of Rank 3

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Abstract

Let M_3 be a free metabelian Lie algebra of rank 3 over a field K . We show that the group of almost tame automorphisms of M_3 is represented as an amalgamated free product of its subgroups. Using an amalgamated free product structure, we give new proof of R. Nauryzbaev's result [R. Nauryzbaev. Reducibility of tame automorphisms of free metabelian Lie algebras of rank 3, Bulletin of L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University, (2009), no. 6, 200—213.] on the reducibility of almost tame automorphisms of M_3 . It immediately follows from this result that almost tame automorphisms of a free metabelian Lie algebras of rank 3 over a constructive field are algorithmically recognizable. We also show that the group generated by all Chein and exponential automorphisms of M_3 has a semi-direct product structure.

The talk is based on the results of joint work with A. Naurazbekova and U. Umirbaev.

Keywords: Free metabelian Lie algebra; Almost tame automorphism; Amalgamated free product.

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Automorphisms and Derivations of a Universal Left-symmetric Enveloping Algebra

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Abstract

Let A_n be an n -dimensional algebra with zero multiplication over a field K of characteristic 0. Then its universal (multiplicative) enveloping algebra U_n in the variety of left-symmetric algebras is a homogeneous quadratic algebra generated by $2n$ elements $l_1, \dots, l_n, r_1, \dots, r_n$, which contains both the polynomial algebra $L_n = K[l_1, \dots, l_n]$ and the free associative algebra $R_n = K[r_1, \dots, r_n]$. We show that the automorphism groups of the polynomial algebra L_n and the algebra U_n are isomorphic for all n is more than 2, based on a detailed analysis of locally nilpotent derivations. In contrast, we show that this isomorphism does not hold for $n=1$, and we provide a complete description of all automorphisms and locally nilpotent derivations of U_1 .

The talk is based on the results of joint work with D. Zhangazanova and U. Umirbaev.

Keywords: Automorphism; Derivation; Left-symmetric algebra; Universal enveloping algebra; Polynomial algebra; Associative algebra.

Acknowledgement: This work was supported by the grant AP23487886 of the Ministry of Science and Higher Education of the Republic of Kazakhstan.

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Possible Automorphism Groups of Some Large Sets

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Abstract

This abstract presents research on large sets, a topic of significant importance in combinatorial theory. We focus on the LS[3,4,14] with parameters $t=3$, $k=4$, and $v=14$, conducting both theoretical and computer-assisted investigations into its potential automorphism group.

Theoretical analyses, informed by the algebraic properties of candidate automorphism groups, were systematically verified and extended through computer-implemented calculations implemented in Java using a customized version of Knuth's Dancing Links algorithm. As a result, new constraints on the possible order of the automorphism group have been established, offering new insights into this potential large set.

Keywords: Large set; Automorphism group.

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p-Adic Non-Existence of Positive Integer Solutions for the Three-Term Exponential Diophantine Equation

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Abstract

This study presents a comprehensive investigation of exponential Diophantine equations involving perfect squares. We examine the fundamental properties of the equation

$$(a^n - 1)(b^n - 1)(c^n - 1) = x^2,$$

which generalizes the classical two-term form

$$(a^n - 1)(b^n - 1) = x^2.$$

New theoretical results are established regarding non-solvability conditions for such equations. In particular, we formulate p-adic valuation-based criteria for the non-existence of positive integer solutions and analyze parity relations among $v_p(a - 1)$, $v_p(b - 1)$, $v_p(c - 1)$, and $v_p(n)$, which lead to contradictions in $v_p(x^2)$. Computational verification for $1 < a < b < c \leq 100$ identifies several prime triples satisfying these criteria, demonstrating that no positive integer solutions exist for specific a, b, c triples. The strongest and most explicit results are obtained in the case $p = 2$; that is, the classical 2-adic setting provides the most powerful criteria for non-existence of solutions.

Keywords: Diophantine equations; 2-adic valuation; Lifting the exponent lemma; Exponential equations.

This study was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Turkey (TÜBİTAK) through the 2210/E Graduate Scholarship Program.

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Fibonacci Points and Inverse Stereographic Projection

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Abstract

In the present study, we investigate the correspondence between Fibonacci structures in the Euclidean plane and their spherical counterparts through the inverse stereographic projection (ISP). The ISP provides a one-to-one mapping that enables the transfer of algebraic and geometric relations from the plane to the sphere. By applying this mapping to Fibonacci points, one can define spherical Fibonacci identities and explore their geometric manifestations on the sphere. Moreover, the sphere can be continuously deformed while preserving a bijective relation between the original and the deformed surfaces. This deformation framework allows the extension of planar Fibonacci identities to generalized spherical geometries, including spheroidal and irregular surfaces. Such deformations can represent naturally occurring shapes, thus establishing a potential connection between Fibonacci-based mathematical identities and biological or physical pattern formation. The proposed approach not only provides a geometric interpretation of Fibonacci identities on curved manifolds but also opens new perspectives for modeling spatial structures in nature through analytical deformations of spherical surfaces.

Keywords: Fibonacci points; Stereographic projection; Deformed spheres; Spirals.

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Determination of Initial Value Function in Time-Fractional Diffusion Equation with Robin Boundary Condition through Hermite Polynomials

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Abstract

This study contributes to establishment of initial value function in a time fractional diffusion equation with robin boundary condition by means of a new approach involving Hermite polynomials, Residual power series method (RPSM) and collocation methods together. First of all, robin boundary condition is made homogeneous by a suitable transformation which reduce the problem to a simpler one. The solution of reduced problem is written in series form in terms of Hermite polynomials which yields a system of fractional differential and algebraic equations. Secondly, RPSM is employed to accomplish approximate solution to the reduced problem which includes some unknowns. At this stage, collocation points and additional data are used together to determine the values of unknown initial value function at collocation points which are the unknowns in the approximate solution. Finally, the initial value of approximate solution yields the unknown initial value function. Two examples are presented to confirm the accuracy and effectiveness of the proposed method.

Keywords: Inverse problem; Time fractional diffusion equation; The robin boundary condition; Hermite collocation method; Residual power series method.

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On the Approximate Solution of the Multi-Term Time-Fractional Diffusion Problem through Hermite Polynomials

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Abstract

This research presents a novel approach for constructing approximate solutions to multi-term time fractional diffusion problems through Hermite polynomials, the Residual Power Series Method (RPSM), and collocation techniques. Initially, the multi-term time fractional diffusion equation is transformed into a single-term equation using the Riemann integral, simplifying the original problem. Next, Hermite polynomials are employed to express the solution as a series, which, through the application of collocation points, reduces the problem to a system of fractional differential and algebraic equations. The RPSM is then applied to determine the unknown coefficient functions in the series representation. By substituting these coefficients back into the series, an approximate solution is constructed. To illustrate the applicability and accuracy of the proposed method, three numerical examples are provided, demonstrating its effectiveness in solving complex fractional diffusion problems.

Keywords: Multi-term time-fractional diffusion equation; Hermite Collocation method; Residual power series method.

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A Septic Hermite Collocation Method for Regularized Long Wave Equation

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Abstract

In this study, a septic Hermite spline collocation method based on the classical Crank–Nicolson approximation is developed for the numerical solution of the regularized long-wave (RLW) equation. To the best of our knowledge, this represents the first application of this approach to the RLW equation. The accuracy and efficiency of the proposed scheme are thoroughly evaluated using the L_2 and L_∞ error norms. Numerical experiments confirm that the method is simple to implement and provides highly accurate results for the RLW equation.

Keywords: Septic Hermite; Collocation method; Crank–Nicolson scheme; RLW equation.

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A Fuzzy Mathematical Decision Model for Residential Rooftop PV Adoption: The HEART Approach

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Abstract

The decreasing cost of photovoltaic (PV) technologies, increasing electricity prices, and evolving environmental concerns have led homeowners to show greater interest in rooftop energy systems. However, adoption decisions depend on multiple economic, technical, and behavioral factors. This study develops a mathematical decision framework to model household investment behavior under uncertainty for Turkey by integrating intuitionistic fuzzy sets with the Hypervolume-based Evaluation and Ranking Technique (HEART). The uncertainty in household preferences is represented through linguistic evaluations provided by decision makers of the study, which are translated into intuitionistic fuzzy sets. The alternatives of decision framework are defined as investing in rooftop PV, rooftop PV with battery storage, and a no-investment baseline. Sensitivity analyses will be conducted to examine the importance of policy instruments such as incentives, financing options, and PV cost reductions which is expected to support policymakers.

Keywords: Investment decision modeling; Rooftop photovoltaics adoption; Multi-criteria decision making.

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Inconvenient and Overlooked Aspects of Using Hydrogen and Electric Propulsion in Transport Vehicles

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Abstract

Currently, hydrogen and electric drives used in various modes of transport are very popular and promising. This article discusses the most important aspects of the operation of electric vehicles (passenger cars) and hydrogen-powered vehicles, including trains. In both cases, the official rationale for using both drives is the possibility of achieving independence from fossil fuel supplies, especially crude oil, which is dictated primarily by political considerations. The publication discusses the acquisition of the main raw materials for lithium-ion batteries in electric cars, as well as methods for obtaining hydrogen as a fuel. It demonstrates that, considering the entire production process of electric cars, especially lithium-ion batteries, the argument about their environmental friendliness cannot be used because it is false. Furthermore, it is pointed out that there is no concept for the use of used batteries. When using hydrogen drives in trains, there is no need to build traction network infrastructure, nor is there any need to monitor its technical condition or make necessary repairs. Of course, it's necessary to build the necessary hydrogen tanks, but similar tanks must also exist to store diesel fuel for diesel locomotives. This article also discusses other possibilities for using hydrogen for transformational purposes, such as the use of combustion engines powered by liquid hydrogen.

Unfortunately, an optimistic approach to this issue prevents a critical perspective. Public debate often leaves no room for scientific arguments, and emotions often prevail.

Keywords: Energy transformation; Energy consumption; Climate policy; Energy in transport; Energy savings.

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Theoretical Investigation of the Change in Amplitude of Acoustic Waves Passing Through a Pipe with a Micron-Sized Roughened Inner Surface

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Abstract

This study theoretically investigates the variation in amplitude of acoustic waves propagating through a cylindrical pipe with a micro-scale roughened inner surface. Based on the principles of linear fluid dynamics, the acoustic wave equation derived from the continuity and Euler equations was used to analytically model attenuation effects caused by viscosity, heat conduction, and surface roughness. In addition to the classical Stokes–Kirchhoff approach, an additional attenuation term (α_r) incorporating the roughness constant, roughness height, and pipe radius was defined. The results demonstrate that surface roughness causes significant energy loss in acoustic amplitude, directly related to frequency, pipe radius, and medium properties. As frequency increases, both viscous and roughness-induced attenuation intensify, while smaller pipe radii enhance boundary-layer effects. These findings reveal that classical acoustic models become inadequate in micro-scale systems and must include surface morphology effects. The study contributes to the literature by introducing an integrated theoretical model incorporating roughness effects into acoustic wave propagation analysis. The results can serve as a fundamental reference for optimizing wave transmission efficiency in microfluidic systems, ultrasonic sensors, biomedical micro-channels, and industrial acoustic diagnostics.

Keywords: Acoustic attenuation; Surface roughness; Microscale fluid dynamics; Acoustic wave propagation; Energy dissipation mechanisms.

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Laser–Material Interaction Dynamics and Surface Topography Optimization on ST52 Steel: Correlation between Friction Coefficient and Maximum Valley Depth (Sv)

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Abstract

To produce a surface morphology with a minimum friction coefficient and maximal valley depth (Sv), this study explores the optimization of laser surface texturing parameters on ST52 structural steel. To determine the physical relationship between frictional behavior and surface topography, controlled adjustments in laser power, scanning area ratio, and pattern shape (square, diamond, hexagonal, and circular) were used to create micron-scale roughness. The resulting surfaces were then examined. The Taguchi method-based experimental design made it possible to identify statistically significant variables affecting Sv and the coefficient of friction. The findings showed that pattern shape (33.58%) and scanning area (30.66%) were the next most significant contributors to frictional performance, after laser power (35.75%).

The maximum Sv value of about 1100 μm , which corresponds to the lowest friction coefficient, was generated by the ideal combination of diamond pattern, 20% scanning area, and 40 W laser power. These results can be explained by the nonlinear interaction between transient heat transport in the substrate and localized energy absorption, which controls the dynamics of resolidification and ablation depth. While excessive thermal input encourages surface smoothing through viscous flow, lower power levels favor deeper micro-valley formation due to less melt convection. The resulting high-Sv topology reduces real contact area and improves lubricant retention, which lowers interfacial shear stresses. These results show that laser texturing is a potent method for creating sophisticated tribological surfaces with great efficiency and durability because careful manipulation of laser parameters allows deterministic control of surface energy, frictional dissipation, and topographical anisotropy.

Keywords: Laser surface texturing; ST52 structural steel; Maximum valley depth (Sv); Friction coefficient optimization; Tribological surface engineering.

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Bi-Static Radar Cross Section for PEC Ellipsoid as a Deformed Sphere

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Abstract

In this study, the bi-static radar cross section (RCS) characteristics of electromagnetic plane wave scattering from perfectly conducting triaxial ellipsoids are investigated. The ellipsoids are treated as perturbed spheres, and the analytical framework previously developed for arbitrarily shaped scatterers [1] is employed. Unlike the backward and forward scattering cases, the bi-static RCS patterns of ellipsoids exhibit significantly different behaviors compared to those of spheres, indicating that spherical results cannot be directly used as an approximation for ellipsoidal geometries. Comprehensive analyses are performed for various ellipsoid sizes, orientations, and aspect ratios, and the resulting RCS variations are examined with respect to both the polar angle θ and the azimuthal angle ϕ . The obtained results reveal that the scattering characteristics are highly dependent on these parameters, especially for non-symmetric configurations. Numerical validations are carried out by comparing the analytical results with full-wave simulations and excellent agreement is observed. These findings highlight the distinct scattering behavior of triaxial ellipsoids and demonstrate the accuracy and applicability of the analytical method in predicting bi-static RCS for non-spherical conducting bodies.

Keywords: Electromagnetic scattering; Bi-Static RCS; Triaxial ellipsoids; Perturbed sphere.

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Theoretical Investigation of Electronic and Spectroscopic Properties of 3-Methoxyquinoxaline-2-carboxylic Acid via DFT

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Abstract

Quinoxaline is an aromatic and planar heterocyclic compound containing two nitrogen atoms. Thanks to its structure, it exhibits various biological activities (such as anticancer, antibacterial, and antiviral) and plays an important role in pharmaceutical research. The nitrogen atoms enable it to form stable complexes with transition metals. Quinoxaline-metal complexes often show higher biological activity than the free ligand forms and are particularly prominent in anticancer drug design. Additionally, these complexes are also utilized in electrochemical and optoelectronic applications. In this study, the electronic and spectroscopic properties of 3-Methoxyquinoxaline-2-carboxylic acid, a quinoxaline derivative, were theoretically investigated using Density Functional Theory (DFT). Initially, the conformers of the molecule were determined using the MMFF molecular mechanics force field in the Spartan software. Among these conformers, the structure with the lowest energy and highest Boltzmann distribution was selected and optimized at the B3LYP/6-311++G(d,p) theory level using the Gaussian 16W program. The electronic properties of the optimized structure were examined through frontier molecular orbitals (HOMO–LUMO), molecular electrostatic potential (MEP) maps, Fukui functions, and charge analyses including APT, NBO, and Hirshfeld methods. These analyses allowed for the evaluation of the molecule's chemical reactivity and the identification of potential nucleophilic and electrophilic sites. In the second phase of the study, the molecule's spectroscopic characterization was carried out, and its vibrational frequencies (IR), NMR, and UV-Vis absorption spectra were calculated. The main purpose of these calculations is to identify the active sites responsible for the formation of potential metal complexes of the molecule and to provide preliminary information regarding their spectroscopic properties.

Keywords: Quinoxaline; DFT; Spectroscopic characterization.

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Nature-Positive Net Present Value for Nigeria: An Eco-Risk-Adjusted Capital Budgeting Framework for Manufacturing and Agribusiness

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Abstract

Traditional capital budgeting in Nigerian firms rarely prices the biodiversity and ecosystem services that materially influence cash flows, downtime, and regulatory risk. We introduce a novel decision tool—Nature-Positive Net Present Value (NP-NPV)—that integrates ecosystem service valuation and an Eco-Risk Beta into project appraisal for manufacturers and agribusinesses operating across the Lagos–Ogun industrial belt, the Niger Delta, and the Cross River rainforest corridor. The framework innovates by: (1) adjusting project cash flows with monetized co-benefits and avoided costs from nature-based interventions (e.g., mangrove and riparian restoration for flood mitigation, wetlands for water purification, pollinator habitat for cocoa, cashew, and sesame yields), using site-specific habitat-hectare shadow pricing; and (2) augmenting WACC with an Eco-Risk Beta derived from geospatial exposure to floodplains, mangrove loss, watershed degradation, and supply-chain biodiversity dependencies. The data pipeline combines firm budgets with open datasets (NIMET rainfall, NIHSA flood hazard, NESREA EPR guidelines, Nigeria’s NBSAP, GBIF pollinator records) and ecosystem service models (InVEST), with uncertainty propagated via Monte Carlo simulation and policy scenarios reflecting Nigeria’s Climate Change Act and AfCFTA export dynamics.

Keywords: Nature-positive NPV; Biodiversity accounting; Ecosystem services valuation.

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Yildiz Technical University, Faculty of Arts and Sciences
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Experimental Optimization of Retinoic Acid Solvent and Serum Conditions for Enhanced Neuronal Differentiation of SH-SY5Y Cells

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Abstract

The SH-SY5Y cell line, a subclone derived from the SK-N-SH human neuroblastoma, is one of the most widely used in vitro models for neuroscience research. It exhibits catecholaminergic characteristics and can differentiate into neuron-like cells under suitable stimuli. Owing to its human origin and responsiveness to chemical inducers, SH-SY5Y is a valuable model for studying neuronal differentiation and mechanisms underlying neurodegenerative disorders, particularly Alzheimer's disease. However, differentiation outcomes strongly depend on experimental conditions, requiring careful optimization.

Retinoic acid (RA) is commonly applied to SH-SY5Y cells to induce neuronal differentiation, as it promotes neurite outgrowth and inhibits proliferation, driving the development of a neuronal-like morphology. Yet, differentiation efficiency is influenced by factors such as the solvent used for RA dissolution and serum concentration during cell seeding. This study optimized two variables: (i) solvent type (ethanol vs. dimethyl sulfoxide [DMSO]) and (ii) fetal bovine serum (FBS) concentration at plating (10%, 5%, or 2.5%). SH-SY5Y cells were seeded at a density of 3×10^5 cells per well in 6-well plates and treated with 10 μ M retinoic acid (RA) in 1% FBS medium from day 2 onwards, with the medium replaced every 48 hours. Ethanol-dissolved RA enhanced neuronal differentiation, with increased neurite length and reduced clustering, whereas DMSO-based RA yielded weaker differentiation. Cultures initiated with 10% FBS displayed the healthiest and most neuron-like morphology. These findings highlight ethanol as a superior solvent for RA-mediated differentiation and suggest that an initial 10% FBS concentration provides optimal conditions for consistent neuronal phenotypes in SH-SY5Y cells.

Keywords: SH-SY5Y differentiation; Retinoic acid; Ethanol vs DMSO; Serum optimization; Neuronal morphology.

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Tribolium Confusum is not so Confused, and will Fly

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Abstract

The confused flour beetle, *Tribolium confusum*, is highly adaptable and evolutionarily successful invasive insect. Although often regarded as a pest, it plays a valuable role as a model organism in genetics and evolutionary biology. The species in the *Tribolium* genus shows distinct morphological and behavioral characteristics, particularly in antenna shape, and was thought not to fly until now.

The *T. confusum* culture was maintained in a 15 cm diameter container with flour and vegetables provided ad libitum. The culture was kept in a well-ventilated environment at 24 °C and 68-70% relative humidity.

To investigate the beetles' response to falling and their potential for flight, several experimental ramps were designed. Beetles were placed on the ramps and encouraged to climb without falling. After several trials, individuals were gently handled to increase stress levels and height awareness.

The *T. confusum* initiated flight or extended their wings while slipping/falling from the ramps, or in response to height stimuli. Most individuals did not stress enough to trigger wing opening during the trials. After handling, 10 of the 20 beetles attempted to flutter their wings from the hand to the prepared surface and many landed upright. Two individuals lifted more than a few millimeters. Only a wing-reflex response was observed on five beetles, and the other five remained unresponsive.

Unlike *T. castaneum*, *T. confusum* is considered flightless due to its weakly developed wings and apparent behavioral reluctance to fly. Previous studies have shown that flight attempts occur only under high-temperature conditions. Here, they attempt to fly solely based on the altitude factor. This ability may have contributed to its past and present distribution, influenced its evolutionary trajectory, and could play a role in future dispersal. Further research should explore this potential through selective breeding experiments.

Keywords: *Tribolium confusum*; Flying beetle; Self-awareness.

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A New Perspective on Milne-type Inequalities involving Riemann–Liouville Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

In this investigation, by utilizing functions whose second derivatives are bounded, we acquire the upper and lower bounds for Milne-type inequalities involving Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals. What's more, we established Milne-type inequalities are examined in detail. Specifically, by choosing specific parameter values, some known results in the literature are generalized.

Keywords: Milne-type inequality; Bounded functions; Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals.

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Fractional Newton-Type Inequalities Involving h-Convex Functions

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Abstract

In this study, Newton-type inequalities involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals have been obtained for a class of functions that are twice differentiable and h-convex. The main step has been to derive an identity that connects the second derivative of the function with its fractional integrals. This identity has been presented as the fundamental for proving new inequalities under the assumption that the function satisfies the condition of h-convexity. The method adopted here is based on analyzing the structure of the second derivative together with the properties of h-convex functions. The definition of h-convexity has allowed a variable to choose where classical convexity may be seen as a special case. By assuming that the second derivative is h-convex on a given interval, estimates have been established that generalize some known results in the literature related to Newton-type inequalities. Tools from classical analysis, such as Hölder's inequality and integral inequalities, have been used in the results obtained.

Keywords: Newton-type inequality; h-convexity; Riemann Liouville fractional integral.

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Generalized Fractional Integral Forms of Newton-Type Inequalities for Functions of Bounded Variation

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive framework for deriving Newton-type inequalities involving generalized fractional integrals for functions of bounded variation. By employing the concept of generalized fractional operators, several new integral inequalities are established, which extend and unify various existing results in the literature. Furthermore, by selecting specific forms of functions and appropriate parameter values, a number of significant special cases are obtained, demonstrating the wide applicability of the proposed approach. The results not only enhance the understanding of fractional inequalities but also provide a broader mathematical foundation for future research in fractional analysis and related areas.

Keywords: Newton-type inequalities; Generalized fractional integrals; Functions of bounded variation.

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New Results on Fractional Simpson-Type Inequalities for Differentiable Convex Functions

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Abstract

Fractional calculus has many applications in various fields such as physics, chemistry, engineering, and mathematics. The use of arithmetic operations from classical analysis in fractional analysis provides more realistic results in solving many problems. In this paper, we establish an identity involving the Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals for differentiable functions. By using this identity, we derive several Simpson-type inequalities for functions whose derivatives in absolute value are convex. Finally, some new results are presented as special cases of the main theorems.

Keywords: Simpson-type inequalities; Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals; Convex functions.

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Development of Weighted Corrected Euler-Maclaurin-Type Inequalities via Fractional Operators for Various Function Classes

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Abstract

This paper presents weighted corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities for diverse function classes by means of Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. To establish our main results, we first derive a fundamental integral identity that incorporates a positive weighted function. The combination of this integral identity with Riemann-Liouville fractional operators yields inequalities applicable to several important function classes, including bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions, functions of bounded variation.

Keywords: Corrected Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities; Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals; Bounded functions; Lipschitzian functions; Functions of bounded variation.

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New Version of Simpson-Type Inequality via Proportional Caputo-Hybrid Operator

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Abstract

Fractional calculus has become an essential analytical tool in modern mathematics and applied sciences, offering refined methods for modeling complex phenomena. In recent years, the field has seen significant growth, particularly with the development of novel fractional operators that enhance modeling capabilities in various scientific and engineering disciplines. The proportional Caputo-hybrid operator represents one of these new developments. In this study, we established new form of Simpson type inequalities within the context of the proportional Caputo-hybrid fractional operator for functions with bounded second and third derivatives. The results are supported by several concrete examples and particular cases, indicating the operator's versatility. This study extends previous contributions in the field and introduces refined tools for the investigation of fractional inequalities and related problems in applied mathematics.

Keywords: Proportional Caputo-Hybrid operator; Simpson-type inequalities; Bounded functions.

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Euler-Maclaurin-Type Inequalities for Generalized Fractional Integrals on Functions of Bounded Variation

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive approach that utilizes generalized fractional integrals to derive Euler–Maclaurin-type inequalities for functions of bounded variation. Moreover, by choosing particular forms of functions and suitable parameters, we obtain several special cases. These cases clearly show the generality and practical applicability of the obtained results. These results not only extend previously known findings but also provide a more general setting for studying such inequalities.

Keywords: Euler-Maclaurin-type inequalities, Generalized fractional integrals; Functions of bounded variation.

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Fractional Differential Shift Encryption: A Caputo-Based Generalization of Dynamic Caesar Ciphering

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Abstract

Classical shift ciphers in general, and Caesar's in particular, are important historical examples of ciphers, but are cryptographically weak due to their fixed key nature and simplicity. Recent efforts to add some strength with analytic shifts add a level of complexity by incorporating calculus into the differential shift cipher. Traditional differentiation takes into account local differences only, so in order to manipulate memory dependence and nonlocal style adaptability, the current project introduces a fractional generalization of the differential shift encryption model. Shifting ciphers, especially Caesar's shifted cipher, are historical applications of ciphermedia, but they have limited security due to fixed keys and a lack of complexity. Recent developments to add some degree of strength with analytic shifts add complexity into the encryption model by allowing principles of calculus to be incorporated into a differential shift cipher. Classic differentiation is limited to local differences, which is the rationale for the current work to create a fractional generalization of a differential shift cipher to change memory dependence and nonlocality in the style of adaptability. Let $F(x)$ be a flag ship function that has continuous derivatives. The instantaneous fractional shift is defined by $k_\alpha(x) = D^\alpha F(x)$, where D^α is Caputo fractional derivative means with order $\alpha \in (0,1]$. Each symbol P_i in the plain text is encrypted by means of an operation over the alphabet using $k_{eff}(x) = \lfloor k_\alpha(x) \rfloor$. The algorithm is then defined numerically using the Grünwald-Letnikov approximation for computational purposes. Let $F(X)$ be a pivotal function that is continuously differentiable. The instantaneous fractional shift is defined by $k_\alpha(x) = D^\alpha F(x)$ where D^α is the Caputo fractional derivative of order $\alpha \in (0,1]$. Each symbol P_i in the plain text is encrypted by means of an operation over the alphabet using k_{eff} . Various simulations for each fractional order α indicate that the encryption strength increases significantly when the system transitions from a localized ($\alpha = 1$) to a memory based ($\alpha < 1$) regime. The statistical entropy, correlation coefficients and key space expansion show a significant enhancement in resisting brute-force and frequency analysis attacks. The Fractional Differential Shift Encryption (FDSE) methodology proposed here in provides a hybrid link between fractional calculus and classical cryptography. Incorporating nonlocal memory and key variation in a dynamic fashion, the FDSE is complex, adding originality in theory and a security advantage in practice. Future work could consider performance with Ψ –Caputo or Atangana-Baleanu operators to generalize to multiple kernels.

Keywords: Fractional calculus; Caputo derivative; Dynamic encryption; Differential cryptography; Nonlocal systems.

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A New Variant of Positive Linear Operators for Convex Functions Providing a Better Error Estimation

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Abstract

Approximation Theory plays a central role in modern mathematical analysis, providing essential tools for studying the behavior of functions and constructing efficient numerical methods. In this work, we contribute to this field by introducing and analyzing a new class of Szász–Mirakjan type operators.

This abstract presents a comprehensive study in Approximation Theory, focusing on the fundamental properties of newly defined Szász–Mirakjan operators. We establish several novel theoretical results that extend existing work in the field. The main contributions of this study are as follows:

- (1) the development of a new framework of positive linear operators of the Szász–Mirakjan type,
- (2) the demonstration that the proposed operators achieve a faster rate of convergence compared to the classical Szász–Mirakjan operators.

The methodology incorporates advanced techniques from mathematical analysis and applied mathematics, with particular emphasis on error analysis.

Keywords: Linear positive operator; Szasz-Mirakjan operators; Voronovskaya-type estimation.

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Some Error Bounds for Milne's Formula via Fractional Integral Operators

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Abstract

This study investigates some Milne-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. Our main goal is to show how such inequalities can be established by using the power mean inequality, and in doing so, we naturally extend several well-known inequalities in the existing literature to more general forms. Moreover, we study special cases of the main theorem by choosing particular functions and parameters. This allows us to see how the general results reduce to simpler and more familiar inequalities. We also provide an illustrative example in order to clarify the use of our results. Furthermore, graphs are included to make the inequalities more understandable and to demonstrate their validity in practice. Overall, this study presents a useful contribution to the theory of inequalities for differentiable convex functions and may serve as a basis for further research.

Keywords: Milne's formula; Quadrature formula; Open Newton-Cotes formulas.

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Milne Formula for Functions of Bounded Variation via Generalized Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

In this paper, some Milne formulas are established by generalized fractional integrals for functions of bounded variation. By choosing particular functions and suitable parameter values, several important special cases can be derived, which clearly illustrate the wide applicability of the proposed approach. This allows us to see how the general results reduce to simpler and more familiar formulas. The results improve the understanding of fractional inequalities and offer a solid mathematical basis for future research in fractional analysis and related fields. Namely, one may consider generalizing our findings by exploring alternative classes of convex functions or different types of fractional integral operators.

Keywords: Milne formula; Functions of bounded variation; Generalized fractional integrals.

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Some Conformable Fractional Newton-type Inequalities via Bounded and Lipschitzian Functions

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Abstract

The core purpose of this study is to investigate some Newton-type inequalities in the framework of conformable fractional operators. These type of inequalities are established for bounded functions and further results are obtained for Lipschitzian functions. In this way, the classical Newton-type inequalities are extended through the perspective of fractional analysis. Moreover, through specific selections of the obtained inequalities, further results are derived, which emphasize the versatility and practical applicability of the proposed approach. Overall, this study adds to the literature on fractional analysis and functional inequalities and also provides a basis for future work in this area.

Keywords: Newton-type inequalities; Bounded functions; Lipschitzian functions.

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Extensions of Newton-Type Inequalities via Multiplicative Conformable Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

In this study, a new Newton-type inequality defined for multiplicative conformable fractional integrals is investigated. This inequality, which has not been previously reported in the literature, is examined within the scope of functions whose multiplicative derivatives are bounded. The inequality is derived using a fundamental identity related to multiplicatively differentiable functions and is reduced to special cases under various operators. Furthermore, the obtained inequality is specialized for multiplicative Riemann–Liouville fractional integrals and multiplicative integrals, and several related inequalities are presented within the framework of these operators.

Keywords: Newton-type inequality; Bounded functions; Multiplicative fractional calculus.

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Some Bullen Type Inequalities for Coordinated s-Convex Functions

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Abstract

Convexity is one of the cornerstones of mathematical analysis and inequality theory. During the last decades, many significant inequalities have been developed for different generalizations of convex functions. In this paper, we establish new Bullen–Simpson type integral inequalities for functions of two variables whose mixed partial derivatives are s-convex in the second sense on the coordinates. Several general results and corollaries are obtained by employing Hölder, Power Mean, and Minkowski inequalities.

Furthermore, the constants involved in these inequalities are explicitly determined, and the classical one-dimensional results are shown to be special cases of our findings. The obtained results provide a comprehensive generalization of the existing Bullen–Simpson type inequalities to the framework of coordinate s-convex functions, offering new insights and potential applications in numerical integration and mean inequalities.

Keywords: Convex functions; Bullen type inequalities; Coordinated convexity.

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Relative Gromov Width with respect to Spheres

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Abstract

In this study, we define different versions of relative Gromov radii with respect to spheres and obtain a result on the displace ability of a Lagrangian submanifold and of the image of a symplectic embedding of a Lagrangian submanifold into $(\mathbb{R}^{2n}, \omega_0)$ under a certain condition. Under this same condition, the Lagrangian submanifold embeds into acylinder with finite radius.

Keywords: Gromov width; Gromov radius; Relative Gromov width; Relative Gromov radius; Lagrangian submanifold; Cylindrical capacity; Displacement energy; Symplectic manifold.

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Neural Network Approaches to High-Order Extensions of Simpson-Type Inequalities

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Abstract

We investigate the the fundamental inequalities approximation, which Erden et al. introduced in literature, is stated in this work. For the previously mentioned classes of functions, the Simpson-type quadrature rules derived from these inequalities are then investigated. The Levenberg–Marquardt (LM) technique is used to train an artificial neural network (ANN) to approximate numerical integration results based on Simpson-type inequalities. It aims to increase the computational accuracy of higher-order derivative-based computations while lowering training error metrics such as Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and Mean Absolute Error (MAE). The results demonstrate that the LM-trained ANN effectively models nonlinear mappings inside Simpson-type inequality frameworks, providing a workable numerical alternative to traditional analytical integration methods. Because it effectively captures the basic relationships between input parameters and their associated integral approximations, this adaptive network may generalize across a range of functional behaviors that are often challenging for traditional approaches to depict. Compared to existing numerical and analytical methods in the literature, this computational design shows improved precision, smoother convergence dynamics, and increased robustness to local minima during the optimization process. Furthermore, the LM-based training approach provides a flexible and scalable approach to extend the applicability of Simpson-type inequalities to more complex domains. Overall, the proposed Levenberg–Marquardt ANN provides a data-driven, flexible, and highly accurate alternative to traditional numerical integration methods. It effectively models complex nonlinear behaviors and extends Simpson-type inequalities into a computational learning framework, offering new potential for hybrid analytical–neural approaches in high-precision quadrature analysis.

Keywords: Simpson-type inequalities; Quadrature rules; Artificial Neural Network (ANN); Levenberg–Marquardt algorithm; Numerical integration; Error analysis; Data-driven modeling.

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Double Fractional Integral Inequalities for Co-ordinated Convex Functions

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Abstract

The primary objective of this study is to establish novel Ostrowski-type fractional integral inequalities for functions whose powers of the absolute values of partial derivatives are convex on the coordinates. By utilizing a fractional integral identity previously proposed in the literature, several generalized versions of these inequalities are derived. In addition, various special cases and related corollaries are provided to emphasize the importance and applicability of the obtained results.

Keywords: Fractional integrals; Co-ordinated convex functions; Ostrowski type inequalities; Double integrals.

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Spherical Fuzzy TOPSIS with Hybrid Entropy-FUCOM Weighting Method

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Abstract

In this study, a novel multi-criteria group decision-making method is developed by integrating subjective and objective weight determination within the framework of spherical fuzzy sets. In the proposed method, the weights of decision-makers are objectively determined by using an entropy measure function, while the criteria weights are calculated through a hybrid approach that combines the FUCOM (Full Consistency Method) and entropy measure function. Thus, both subjective assessments (via FUCOM) and objective measures (via entropy) are simultaneously considered in determining the importance of the criteria. Then, this approach is integrated with the TOPSIS method in the spherical fuzzy environment. The proposed method provides a more balanced and consistent weighting system, enabling a comprehensive evaluation of different perspectives in decision-making processes. To demonstrate its applicability, the method is applied to a real-life problem and explained step by step. Moreover, several entropy measures from the literature are integrated into the proposed approach to perform a sensitivity analysis based on the obtained results. This analysis allows for evaluating the performance and robustness of the method under various conditions, offering an extensive comparison.

Keywords: Objective weighting; Subjective weighting; Hybrid weighting; Entropy; FUCOM, TOPSIS.

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Closed-form Solution for FGM Plates via using CUF and Boundary Discontinuous Fourier Method

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Abstract

This abstract presents a study on the static analysis of fully clamped plates made from functionally graded materials, utilizing the Carrera Unified Formulation (CUF) in conjunction with the boundary-discontinuous Fourier method. The CUF models the displacement field with expansion orders ranging from 1 to 4 through an Equivalent Single-Layer (ESL) approach. The material properties change exponentially and follow a power-law distribution across the plate's thickness and are expressed using Taylor functions. The governing equilibrium equations and boundary conditions are derived using the virtual displacements principle and resolved using the boundary-discontinuous Fourier series approach. To validate the results, we compare the results with existing solutions, highlighting the benefits of using variable kinematic models for analyzing functionally graded plates. The research examines how varying porosity distributions, porosity ratios, volume fraction coefficients, and diverse types of functionally graded materials influence the mechanical properties of these structures. This approach offers a distinctive framework that can act as a reference standard for verifying novel plate theories and finite element models.

Keywords: CUF; Closed-form solution; Boundary discontinuous model; Boundary discontinuous; FG Plate.

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Curvature Properties of Spherical Product Hypersurfaces in Minkowski Space

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Abstract

In this study, we investigate a special family of hypersurfaces generated via the spherical product of planar curves within the context of four-dimensional Minkowski space E_1^4 . We derive explicit expressions for the Gaussian and mean curvatures of these hypersurfaces and establish the necessary and sufficient conditions under which they become flat or minimal. This analysis reveals rich geometric structures and highlights how the ambient Lorentzian metric influences curvature behavior. Our findings provide a foundational step toward a broader understanding of spherical product hypersurfaces in non-Euclidean settings.

Keywords: Hypersurface; Minkowski space; Spherical product.

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The q-Frame DNA Strand Helix and its Spherical Indicatrices

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Abstract

This study examines the geometry of the DNA strand helix through the q-frame (quasi-frame), a moving frame that remains well defined even at points of vanishing curvature and does not require arc-length parametrization. We derive q-frame vectors of the DNA strand helix and their corresponding curvature functions. For each vector, we construct the associated spherical indicatrix and generate visualizations. This work contributes to the theoretical framework, which may be useful in mathematical biology.

Keywords: q-Frame; DNA Strand Helix; Spherical Indicatrices; Mathematical Modeling.

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Mathematical Modeling and Dynamic Analysis of an Epidemic System Based on the SIR Framework

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Abstract

In this study, we propose a mathematical model to analyze the impact of epidemics on population dynamics. In the classical SIR framework, the population is divided into three segments: susceptible (S), infected (I), and recovered (R). However, changes in the recovery process, immune acquisition, and incidence and treatment functions can significantly alter the system's behavior. Considering these aspects, we develop a new epidemic model that incorporates these factors to provide a more realistic representation of disease transmission. The stability and dynamic behavior of the proposed model are theoretically analyzed, and the obtained results are supported by numerical simulations. Finally, the mathematical findings are interpreted from a biological perspective, highlighting the model's potential implications for epidemic prevention and control.

Keywords: SIR Model; Stability analysis; Mathematical modeling.

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A Note on Fractional Simpson-like Type Inequality for Functions whose Second Derivatives are of Bounded Variation

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Abstract

In this study, a Simpson-like type equality for the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral is established. Using this equality, several fractional Simpson-type inequalities are proved for functions whose second derivatives are of bounded variation.

Keywords: Fractional integrals; Simpson-type inequality; Bounded variation.

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An Algorithm for the Singular Value Decomposition of Matrices with Commutative Hypercomplex Entries and Applications

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Abstract

We develop and analyze an SVD procedure for matrices whose entries belong to commutative hypercomplex algebras, with a concrete instantiation on elliptic quaternions. The method exploits a structure-preserving complex representation that transports SVD computation to standard complex linear-algebra routines and then maps the factors back to the hypercomplex setting. This representation preserves rank and singular values, so the resulting decomposition supports canonical constructions such as the Moore–Penrose pseudoinverse and minimum-norm least-squares solutions without leaving the algebraic framework. We outline practical algorithms for computing the SVD, pseudoinverse, and least-squares solves over elliptic quaternions, and we discuss numerical behavior inherited from the stability of complex SVD implementations. Illustrative experiments demonstrate consistent decompositions and accurate solutions across representative problem instances. The framework supports applications in image processing, signal processing, and digital watermarking.

Keywords: Quaternion matrix; Singular value decomposition; Pseudoinverse; Least squares solution.

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Generalized Chebyshev Polynomials

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Abstract

In this study, we present first and second type of generalized Chebyshev polynomials. First, we generalize the first and second type of Chebyshev equations by using a positive parameter k . Then, we find the solutions of new Chebyshev equations using the k -hypergeometric equation which is defined as

$$kz(1 - kz)y'' + [c - (a + b + k)kz]y' - aby = 0,$$

where $k > 0$. The k -hypergeometric function is satisfy the k -hypergeometric equation and defined as follows

$$F_k(a, b; c; z) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_{n,k}(b)_{n,k}}{(c)_{n,k}} z^n,$$

where the k -Pochhammer symbol $(m)_{n,k}$ is defined as

$$(m)_{n,k} = m(m + k)(m + 2k) \dots (m + (n - 1)k),$$

and $m \in \mathbb{C}, k \in \mathbb{R}$ and $n \in \mathbb{N}^+$ and $(m)_{0,k} = 1$. Second, we define new first and second type of generalized Chebyshev polynomials. After that, we derive certain type explicit formulas and generating function relations for the first and second type of generalized Chebyshev polynomials. Using these relations, we give some multilateral and multilinear generating function families for the first and second type of generalized Chebyshev polynomials. We also show some examples for these multilateral and multilinear generating function relations.

Keywords: Chebyshev polynomials; k -hypergeometric equation; Generating function.

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CR-Fuzzy Soft Matrices: A New Structure for Modelling Uncertainty and Group Decision-Making

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Abstract

Uncertainty is an essential feature of many practical problems, and classical set-based models often fall short of capturing the nuances it creates. Over time, several generalizations such as fuzzy, intuitionistic fuzzy, and soft sets have been developed to represent imprecision, hesitation, and parameter-dependent information more effectively. Their combined forms offer richer structures for handling complex relationships between elements and parameters.

In this study, we introduce CR-fuzzy soft matrices, which extend CR-fuzzy soft sets to a matrix-based structure, allowing for a more systematic representation and computation. Basic operations—including addition, subtraction, multiplication, complement, and transposition—are defined, and several commonly used matrix types (row, column, square, diagonal, symmetric, zero, and absolute matrices) are characterized within this setting.

We also present a method that uses these matrices to support group decision-making under uncertainty by merging the assessments of multiple decision-makers in a structured manner. A case study on home selection illustrates how the approach can be applied in practice.

Keywords: Soft sets; CR-Fuzzy soft sets; CR-Fuzzy soft matrix.

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Modular Fuzzy Metric-like Spaces

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to describe the concept of modular fuzzy metric-like space. This space is a combination of modular-like metric space and fuzzy metric-like space. We give examples and propositions to validate the superiority of this new concept. We also show that, in a modular fuzzy metric-like space, the limit of the convergent sequence may not be unique.

Keywords: Metric-like space; Fuzzy metric space; Fuzzy metric-like space; Modular-like metric space; Modular fuzzy metric-like space.

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A Variational Approach to Generalized Offset Surfaces in Minkowski Space

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Abstract

This study presents the generalized offset surface definition for non-degenerate diagonalizable surfaces in Minkowski space and its ϵ -neighbourhood analysis. Through this new definition, the fundamental properties of generalized and standard offset surfaces in Minkowski geometry are examined. The work also includes an investigation of the first variation of the Gaussian and mean curvatures between the original surface and the standard offset surface in Minkowski space, and an exploration of specific conditions under which these variations show distinct properties. Furthermore, a comprehensive analysis of the first variation, the Gauss formula related to the first variation, and the second variation for the floor space of standard offset surfaces in Minkowski space is presented. Furthermore, the relevant findings are supported by examples and graphics. Consequently, it is considered that the findings of the study provide mathematical structures for differential geometry and physics, while also addressing the needs encountered in engineering design applications.

Keywords: Minkowski space; Generalized offset surfaces; Standard offset surfaces; Variations of floor space.

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Block-Scale Steganography in Color Images

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Abstract

Today, ensuring the secure transmission of data over the internet is of great importance, as there is a risk that original data may be accessed by unauthorized third parties. The aim of this study is to develop a method that enhances data security by using the steganography technique to protect confidential and personal information from unauthorized access. Steganography is a technique in which ordinary images are used as carriers to store information in a concealed manner. In this method, the sender must select an appropriate carrier image, message content, and encryption key when determining the message to be hidden. The primary goal of steganography is to ensure secure data storage without introducing any noticeable changes to the image in which the message is embedded. Considering the studies conducted in the literature on data hiding, RGB image data and the wavelet transform—one of the multi-scale methods developed in recent years—constitute the focus of this research.

In this study, the data to be concealed is an RGB image, which is divided into blocks using a matrix-column-based approach. A cover image was selected for each block, and these blocks were embedded into the cover images using the Haar wavelet transform. Finally, the blocks obtained from the cover images were combined to reconstruct the secret image. The Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR) and Structural Similarity Index Method (SSIM) values were examined to compare the original secret image and the reconstructed image.

Keywords: Steganography; Wavelet transform; color image.

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Measurement of Radon Gas in the Vicinity of the Adalar Segment of the North Anatolian Fault

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Abstract

The prediction of seismic events encompasses a range of parameters, including magnitude, geographical location, and temporal considerations. While the determination of location and magnitude can be made to a certain degree in the present, temporal predictions must be expressed in long intervals. This underscores the critical importance of short-term prediction. A substantial body of research has identified a correlation between variations in radon gas concentrations, both prior to and following seismic events, and seismic activity. A major earthquake is anticipated in the Adalar and Avclar segments of the North Anatolian Fault, situated within the Sea of Marmara (a region previously impacted by the 1912 Ganos and 1999 Kocaeli earthquakes).

In this study, radon concentration and temperature, humidity, and pressure data were collected in a continuous manner. This data was collected using a station that was to be established on the Anatolian plate in the Adalar segment. The relationship between radon anomalies and earthquakes was investigated using these data. The cause of the radon anomalies that occurred was determined, and their relationship with geological activity was analyzed. The rise in radon concentration that began on August 11, 2025, and persisted until the 15 August 2024, 06:20 magnitude 3.8 earthquake in Mudanya, Bursa, has been linked to the seismic event.

Keywords: Soil radon concentration; Earthquake; Alpha guard radon monitor.

Acknowledgement: This study was supported by the Scientific and Technological Research Council of Türkiye (TÜBİTAK) under Project No. 123Y145.

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Design and Thermal Analysis of a Target for Simultaneous ^{152}Tb / ^{155}Tb Production via Alpha Induced Reactions

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Abstract

A considerable body of research has recently been devoted to the investigation of terbium radioisotopes and their potential for use in both therapeutic and diagnostic applications in the field of nuclear medicine. While experimental studies have commenced, the necessary information for the commercial production of Terbium isotopes in accelerators has yet to be obtained. In this study, a target design was proposed for the simultaneous production of ^{152}Tb and ^{155}Tb isotopes using enriched Europium targets. The thermal analysis of this design was performed according to different accelerator parameters. Consequently, the cooling requirements necessary for optimal isotopic fraction and activation were calculated, and the practical limits of the target design were determined.

Keywords: Tb-152; Tb-155; Target design; Alpha induced reactions.

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Neutron Imaging Applications

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Abstract

The discovery of the neutron in 1932 not only made it possible for humanity to access nuclear energy over time but also enabled the use of neutrons as a probe in existing material inspection methods and led to the development of new techniques. One such technique is neutron imaging, a powerful nondestructive evaluation method. In this technique, neutrons sent toward a sample undergo various reactions, such as elastic scattering and capture, and the neutrons that pass through the sample are captured by a detector that generates signals which are eventually converted into an image. A typical digital neutron imaging system consists of a neutron source, a scintillator, and a charge-coupled device (CCD) camera that collects the visible-light data produced by the scintillator and converts it into a radiograph. Neutron computed tomography (nCT) involves combining many radiographs acquired from different angles of the sample, enabling full 3D inspection. Unlike X-rays, neutrons interact with atomic nuclei, making neutron and X-ray imaging complementary. Because neutrons interact with nuclei, they can reveal low-Z materials hidden behind high-Z materials. Neutron imaging therefore finds applications in many fields, including the nuclear industry, energy storage systems, national security, and archeology. Additionally, it is used to examine defects in additively manufactured materials that contain both low- and high-Z elements. In such materials, resolving sub-millimeter features is possible using fast neutrons, with minimal nuclear transmutation occurring in the inspected components.

Keywords: Neutron imaging; Neutron computed tomography; Scintillator.

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Error Bounds for Boole's Type Inequalities via Tempered Fractional Operators with Numerical Analysis

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Abstract

The study of numerical analysis and fractional integral inequalities facilitates the precise error evaluation and accuracy of the stability of numerical integration formulas in computational schemes. In this study, we formulate novel Boole-type inequalities for differentiable convex functions within the framework of tempered fractional integrals. Initially, we establish an integral identity within the context of tempered fractional integrals. Through the utilization of this identity, we derive several Boole's type inequalities for differentiable convex mappings associated with tempered fractional integrals. We obtain unique Boole's type inequalities by leveraging significant mathematical tools such as Holder's and power mean inequality, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains. To demonstrate the practical and theoretical implications, we present concrete examples derived from the established results, emphasizing their significance in fractional calculus and its broader applications.

Keywords: Boole's formula type inequality; Convex function; Tempered fractional integrals.

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Enhanced Fractional Boole's Type Inequalities for Differentiable Convex Functions using Tempered Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

Fractional calculus generalizes classical differentiation and integration of arbitrary order. It offers practical analytical approaches for defining complex phenomena exhibiting nonlocal behavior and memory. This investigation introduces unique inequalities for convex functions employing tempered fractional integrals, focusing on Boole's type inequalities. A significant equality is formulated within the framework of tempered fractional integrals. Based on this identity, we develop various Boole-type inequalities for differentiable convex mappings connected with tempered fractional integrals. These mappings extend the applicability of fractional calculus by extending classical notions and presenting further insight into the behavior of convex functions. We attain distinctive types of Boole's type inequalities by incorporating key mathematical techniques such as bounded functions, Lipschitzian functions, and functions with bounded variation, improving the practical applicability of these inequalities in various mathematical realms. The practical relevance and theoretical implications of the findings are demonstrated through concrete examples obtained from the newly obtained theorems, highlighting their significance in fractional calculus and its larger applications.

Keywords: Boole's formula type inequality; Convex function; Tempered fractional integrals; Lipschitzian function; Bounded variation.

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Fractional Calculus Approach to Perturbed Trapezoid-Type Inequalities: Novel Error Estimates and Application

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Abstract

Inequalities involving fractional operators have also been an active area of research. These inequalities play a crucial role in establishing bounds, estimates, and stability conditions for solutions to fractional integrals. The main aim in the current article is to establish an identity through the Caputo Fabrizio integral operator. By using this identity, we are obtained the new fractional bounds and error estimated for the perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities. With the aid of this identity, it is proved that new fractional perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities for functions whose third derivatives in absolute value are convex. In addition, the research has acquired fractional perturbed trapezoid type inequalities for (α, m) -convex function. This is the first article for fractional version of perturbed trapezoid-type inequalities. Finally, we present several corollaries to demonstrate how new results are better than previous results. Moreover, we have given application to the quadrature formula.

Keywords: Perturbed trapezoid type inequality; (α, m) -convex function; Fractional integrals; Young's inequality.

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Improved Bounds for Ostrowski's Type Inequalities via a Generalized Montgomery Identity

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Abstract

Integral inequalities have applications in numerical integration, approximation theory, error analysis, fractional calculus, optimization techniques and applied mathematical modeling. In this work, a generalized Montgomery-type identity is used to derive refined Ostrowski-type integral inequalities. The proposed methodology yields more precise and adaptable bounds that extend several existing results and enhance analytical accuracy. A comparative assessment indicates that the established inequalities provide narrower error margins and superior computational reliability compared to prior contributions. Moreover, graphical and numerical illustrations are presented to substantiate the validity of the derived outcomes.

Keywords: Ostrowski-type inequality; Chebyshev–Grüss inequality; Montgomery identity; Chebyshev functional; Numerical integration.

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Advancements in Weddle's Formula for Tempered Fractional Integrals: Applications in Numerical Integration

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Abstract

Tempered fractional integrals arise naturally in the modeling of anomalous diffusion, viscoelastic phenomena, and other processes in modern physics. In this study, we provides a comprehensive derivation of integral inequalities for differentiable convex functions in the context of tempered fractional integrals. Initially, we formulate significant integral identity involving tempered fractional integrals, which are subsequently used to establish Weddle's type inequalities for differentiable convex functions. Furthermore, numerical demonstrations and graphical representations to affirm the validity and relevance of these newly derived inequalities within the tempered fractional integral framework are presented.

Keywords: Convexity; Weddle's formula; Fractional calculus; Tempered fractional integrals.

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Novel Parameterized Quadrature Formulas Type Inequalities and Their Applications

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Abstract

Numerical integration plays a crucial role in the theory of integral inequalities, providing a rigorous framework for establishing accurate error bounds and analytical estimates. To strengthen the theoretical foundation of quadrature rules in this investigation, we derived a unique parameterized equality that formulates a family of quadrature formulas. Employing this equality, we obtain numerous inequalities for functions whose derivatives, in absolute value, are convex. These proposed inequalities generalize and extend well-known results, including trapezoid, midpoint, Simpson, Milne, and Boole-type inequalities that have been previously studied in the literature. The theoretical developments are complemented by numerical illustrations and graphical analysis to confirm the significance of established inequalities. These results are particularly significant for estimating error bounds in quadrature formulas, offering refined tools for advancing the precision of numerical integration techniques.

Keywords: Convexity; Boole's formula; Quadrature formulas; Error bounds.

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New Results on Weddle's Type Inequalities Involving Tempered Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

Integral inequalities represent a central component of modern mathematical analysis, providing essential connections between theory and various applied disciplines. This study develops new inequalities for convex functions through the use of tempered fractional integrals, employing a known integral identity as the basis of the investigation. In particular, we establish Weddle's type inequalities for differentiable convex functions and extend the results to critical functional classes, such as Lipschitzian functions, bounded functions, and functions with bounded variation. These developments not only enhance the theoretical framework of fractional calculus but also provide potential applications in computational analysis and numerical integration.

Keywords: Convexity; Weddle's formula; Bounded functions; Tempered fractional integrals.

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A Study on Boole's-Type Inequalities within the Framework of Caputo Fractional Operators

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Abstract

The theory of integral inequalities facilitates the derivation of error bounds and estimation techniques. By focusing on differentiable convex functions, this study establishes a novel integral equality using the Caputo fractional integral operator, which plays a central role in deriving numerous novel Boole-type inequalities. Utilizing properties of the Caputo fractional integral, refined inequalities with tighter bounds and increased accuracy are achieved. These results extend classical Boole's inequalities and include applications involving special functions, such as the Mittag-Leffler and q-Polygamma functions. The suggested results bring improved accuracy in error estimation and advance fractional calculus, with potential applications in numerical analysis and optimization.

Keywords: Convexity; Boole's formula; Caputo fractional integrals; Fractional calculus.

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Novel Approaches to Dual Simpson-Type Inequalities via Caputo-Fabrizio Fractional Operators for Different Classes of Functions and Application

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Abstract

Integral inequalities are indeed a powerful tool in the context of numerical integration and quadrature methods. The study of fractional calculus continues to be an active area of research with practical implications for real-world applications. When combined with fractional operators, these integral inequalities become even more valuable in the analysis and estimation of errors in fractional calculus. The Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operator is one of the key concepts in fractional calculus. In the present study, we established a new identity through the fractional operator. By using this novel identity, some new error estimations of dual-Simpson type inequalities are obtained for the case of differentiable functions. Based on this identity, dual-Simpson type inequalities are proved for bounded as well as Lipschitzian functions. In addition, we demonstrate an application of our findings to the quadrature formula.

Keywords: Dual Simpson-type inequalities; Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integrals; s-Convex function; Hölder's inequality; Power-mean inequality; Young's inequality; Bounded function; Lipschitzian function; Quadrature formula.

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Novel Results on Fractional Weddle's Type Inequalities for Several Functional Classes via Tempered Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

The theory of inequalities forms the backbone of analysis by refining essential estimates between functions and their means. Weddle's type inequalities yield sharper error estimates and enhance the precision of the accuracy of integral approximation techniques. It serves as a cornerstone for improvements in mathematical modeling and integral calculus. In this investigation, we derive unique inequalities for convex functions employing tempered fractional integrals, concentrating on Weddle's type inequalities. A significant equality is formulated within the framework of tempered fractional integrals, and this provides the cornerstone for our study. Based on this equality, we develop various Weddle-type inequalities for differentiable convex mappings connected with tempered fractional integrals. These mappings extend the applicability of fractional calculus by extending classical notions and presenting further insight into the behavior of convex functions. We attain distinctive types of Weddle's type inequalities by involving key mathematical tools such as Lipschitzian, bounded functions, and functions with bounded variation, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains. To exemplify the practical and theoretical consequences of the findings, we provide concrete examples obtained from the established theorems, focusing on their significance in fractional calculus and its larger applications.

Keywords: Weddle's formula type inequality; Lipschitzian functions; Bounded functions; Bounded variation; Tempered fractional integrals.

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Refinement of Weddle's-Type Inequalities via Tempered Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

Fractional calculus generalizes classical differentiation and integration of arbitrary order. It offers practical analytical tools for describing complex phenomena exhibiting memory and nonlocal behavior. This investigation introduces unique inequalities for convex functions employing tempered fractional integrals, focusing on Weddle's type inequalities. A significant equality is formulated within the framework of tempered fractional integrals. Based on this identity, we develop various Weddle-type inequalities for differentiable convex mappings connected with tempered fractional integrals. These mappings extend the applicability of fractional calculus by extending classical notions and presenting further insight into the behavior of convex functions. We attain distinctive types of Weddle's type inequalities by involving key mathematical tools such as Holder's and power mean inequality, enhancing the implementation of these inequalities in diverse mathematical domains. To exemplify the practical and theoretical consequences of the findings, we provide concrete examples obtained from the established theorems, focusing on their significance in fractional calculus and its larger applications.

Keywords: Weddle's formula type inequality; Convex function; Tempered fractional integrals.

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New Milne-Type Inequalities for Lipschitzian Functions by Conformable Fractional Operators

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Abstract

In this paper, new Milne-type inequalities are proved by conformable fractional operators for Lipschitzian functions. Moreover, some results are presented by using specific functions and suitable parameters of the obtained theorem. This shows how the general results reduce to simpler and more familiar inequalities. Furthermore, these results may be further generalized by examining other classes of convex functions or by employing different fractional integral operators.

Keywords: Milne-type inequalities; Lipschitzian functions; Conformable fractional operators.

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On Estimation of the Bullen-Mercer Inequality

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Abstract

This paper establishes Bullen-Mercer inequality for h -convex functions with Riemann-Liouville fractional operators. The subject is a novel fractional variant of the existing Bullen-Mercer type inequalities, with easy computations using the B-function. Furthermore, novel results on Bullen-Mercer-type inequalities for bounded and Lipschitzian functions are discussed.

Keywords: h -convex function; Bullen inequality; B-function; Mercer inequality.

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A Study on Maclaurin Type Inequalities via P -Mapping and Its Applications

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Abstract

The aim of this study is to investigate Maclaurin's type inequalities via P -mapping. For this purpose of investigation, firstly, we recall an identity and some interesting inequalities of Maclaurin's type, which were proved by Cortez et al. in [A new approach to error inequalities: From Euler-Maclaurin bounds to cubically convergent algorithm]. Then, by considering this identity as a primary result, we obtained some new variants of Maclaurin-type inequalities in the context of P -mapping. Furthermore, we provide a comparative analysis between P -mapping and classical convex mapping through graphically and numerically. To show the significance of our results, we also give some interesting applications of our main findings.

Keywords: Integral inequalities; P -mapping; Maclaurin inequality.

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Comparative Analysis of Higher-Order Neural Networks and Kernel-Based Nonlinear Arps Models for Forecasting Cumulative Oil Production

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Abstract

For petroleum reservoir management and production techniques to be optimized, cumulative oil production forecasts must be accurate. Using production data from a sandstone reservoir in the Cambay Basin, Gujarat, India, this comparative study examines the predicted performance of two sophisticated modeling techniques: the Nonlinear Extension of the Arps Decline Model (NEA) and the Higher-Order Neural Network (HONN). By encoding both linear and nonlinear correlations of input parameters, the HONN technique improves on the capabilities of traditional neural networks and makes learning effective even with sparse training data. By incorporating kernel approaches into the conventional Arps decline formulation, the NEA model, on the other hand, allows for a nonlinear multivariate structure that captures intricate reservoir dynamics while preserving computing simplicity via a one-step linear recursion. Field production data that had been pre-processed and noise-filtered was used to train and evaluate both models. Forecast accuracy, robustness to sparse data, and generalizability over nonstationary production trends were used to assess comparative performance. The findings show that the NEA model exhibits higher stability and interpretability for long-term production decrease analysis, whereas HONN offers superior adaptation to nonlinear data patterns and produces extremely accurate short-term projections. The work emphasizes how data-driven neural techniques and kernel-based decline models complement each other in improving the accuracy of production forecasting in the context of limited data, which is common in Indian petroleum reservoirs.

Keywords: Oil production forecasting; Time series; Higher-order neural networks; Higher-order synaptic operation; Kernel method; Arps decline; Multivariate regression.

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Mathematical Modeling of the Calendering Process of Temperature-Dependent Non-Newtonian Fluids Using a PyTorch Neural Network Viscosity

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Abstract

The aim of this research is to establish a PyTorch-based deep neural network model capable of predicting the velocity and temperature distributions in the calendering of incompressible, non-Newtonian fluids with temperature-dependent viscosity. The governing partial differential equations are first non-dimensionalized using suitable scaling variables and then simplified through lubrication theory, reducing them to a set of nonlinear ordinary differential equations. Analytical expressions for pressure, velocity, and temperature are derived using perturbation techniques. Important engineering parameters, including detachment point, final sheet thickness, roll separating force, power consumption, Nusselt number, and streamlines—are computed using the Regula Falsi method and numerical quadrature. The symbolic solutions are plotted to examine the effects of key physical parameters. A deep neural network is implemented in Python using the PyTorch framework, incorporating sigmoid activation functions. The model's predictive capability is evaluated using training loss curves, absolute error measurements, and comparative visualization through bar charts. The framework achieves remarkable precision, with mean squared error values of 2.1×10^{-4} , 6.3×10^{-4} , 4.8×10^{-4} , 8.5×10^{-4} for velocity profiles and 3.4×10^{-4} , 5.1×10^{-4} , 3.9×10^{-4} , 7.2×10^{-4} for temperature profiles, with coefficients of determination $R^2 > 0.98$ for both cases. Furthermore, the effects of significant non-dimensional parameters on convective heat transfer are examined through variations in the Nusselt number. The findings demonstrate that an increase in the Weissenberg number enhances heat transfer performance, whereas a rise in the material parameter results in a reduction. Additionally, a higher Brinkman number leads to a decrease in both sheet thickness and power consumption. The developed framework supports real-time optimization of polymer sheet geometries, minimizes roll separation forces in rubber manufacturing, and promotes energy-efficient processing in advanced coating and nanomaterial applications.

Keywords: PyTorch; Artificial neural Networks; Calendering; non-Newtonian fluid model; Temperature-dependent viscosity; approximation solution.

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Existence and Uniqueness of Solutions for Time-variable Fractional Differential Equations

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Abstract

In this talk, we investigate a nonlinear initial value problem involving a Caputo fractional derivative whose order is a continuous and nondecreasing function of time. By employing a successive approximation method, we construct a sequence of functions and prove, using the Arzelà-Ascoli theorem, that this sequence converges uniformly to a solution. A Lipschitz-type condition on the nonlinear term ensures uniqueness, with a computable constant that guarantees the contraction property. An illustrative example confirms that the imposed conditions are satisfied in practice, thereby validating the theoretical results.

Keywords: Fractional differential equation; Caputo derivative; Existence of solution; Uniqueness of solution.

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Exponential Stability for Coupled Lamé System with a Fractional Derivative Time Delay

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Abstract

We develop a detailed analysis for a coupled Lamé system with fractional time delay. We show by using a semigroup approach and the well-known Dafermos auxiliary variable, that the system is well-posed. Moreover, we analyze stability issue for the considered system. Namely, under a suitable choice of Lyapunov functional, exponential decay of the whole energy holds.

The study of the Lamé system of elastostatics equipped with various boundary conditions (Dirichlet, Neumann and mixed type) takes an important place in mathematical and engineering literature. Subsequent efforts to increase the range of its applicability of the mathematical theory developed in this direction have led to the consideration of more general type of systems. Thus, our paper concerns with the study of two coupled Lamé systems where the fractional damping term with time delay is focused in one component for system (1.1) and two components for system (1.2).

Theses systems are given by:

$$\begin{cases} u_1''(x,t) + \alpha u_2(x,t) - \Delta_e u_1(x,t) + \mu_1 u_1'(x,t) + a \partial_t^{\beta,k} \mu_1 u_1'(x,t - \tau) = 0, & \text{in } \Omega \times \mathbb{R}_+^* \\ u_2''(x,t) + \alpha u_1(x,t) - \Delta_e u_2(x,t) + \mu_1 u_2'(x,t) = 0 & , \text{in } \Omega \times \mathbb{R}_+^* \end{cases} \quad (1.1)$$

and

$$\begin{cases} u_1''(x,t) + \alpha u_2(x,t) - \Delta_e u_1(x,t) + \mu_1 u_1'(x,t) + a \partial_t^{\beta,k} \mu_1 u_1'(x,t - \tau) = 0, & \text{in } \Omega \times \mathbb{R}_+^* \\ u_2''(x,t) + \alpha u_1(x,t) - \Delta_e u_2(x,t) + \mu_2 u_2'(x,t) + b \partial_t^{\beta,k} \mu_2 u_2'(x,t - \tau) = 0, & \text{in } \Omega \times \mathbb{R}_+^* \end{cases} \quad (1.2)$$

Keywords: Wave equation; Coupled system; Lyapunov function; Fractional time delay.

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A Positivity-Preserving Numerical Scheme for Reaction–Diffusion SIRA Models of Cyber-Epidemics

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Abstract

This abstract presents a comprehensive study of mathematical models for understanding and controlling cyber-epidemics. We investigate the fundamental properties of an extended Susceptible-Infected-Removed-Antidotal (SIRA) model within a reaction-diffusion framework and establish new theoretical results that extend previous work in the field. Our main contributions include: (1) the development of a novel mathematical framework for capturing both local infection dynamics and spatial transmission of malware across networks, (2) the proof of conditions for boundedness and convergence of the discrete system based on M-matrix theory, and (3) applications to cyber security strategies for antivirus deployment optimization and outbreak containment.

The methodology employs advanced techniques from numerical analysis and stability theory including a semi-implicit numerical scheme that treats diffusion terms implicitly and reaction terms explicitly, coupled with Nonstandard Finite Difference (NSFD) techniques.

Keywords: Computer virus model; Reaction-diffusion; Semi-implicit; Stability analysis; Operator splitting; NSFD scheme.

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Analysis of Dynamic Temperature Characteristics of Gearbox Transmission System of Wind Turbine

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Abstract

Gear transmission systems are widely employed in wind power, aerospace, automotive, marine, and heavy machinery industries due to their high efficiency, stability, and load capacity. In wind turbines, they regulate speed and torque to optimize generator performance. However, gearboxes remain prone to failures nearly 48% of total turbine faults primarily due to excessive temperature rise that degrades lubrication and reduces efficiency. This study investigates the thermal behavior of a wind turbine gear-bearing-rotor system through a combination of numerical simulations and experimental validation. A dynamic model is developed using the lumped parameter method, followed by a finite element thermal model incorporating translation–torsion coupling and frictional heat generation. The model predicts temperature distributions and identifies hotspots, mainly around the high-speed shaft bearing and gear. Comparative analysis under wind and non-wind conditions reveals that input speed and wind loading significantly influence thermal response, exhibiting exponential trends with increasing speed. Results validated with SCADA data show strong agreement with theoretical predictions, confirming the model's reliability. The proposed method offers an effective approach for thermal monitoring and optimization of wind turbine gearboxes, enhancing operational reliability and lifespan.

Keywords: Wind turbine; Gear transmission; Thermal analysis; Finite element; Wind load; Temperature distributio.

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Performance Analysis of Multi Unit Distributed System with Internet Service Providers

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Abstract

In this present study series-parallel system composed of three subsystems with the following specifications are analyzed: subsystem 1 consists of three dissimilar clients connected to two dissimilar internet service providers (ISPs) which made up subsystem 2, whereas subsystem 3 consist of a single unit active server. Clients, internet service providers and server's failure rate β_i ($i = 0,1,2,3$) and repair rate α_j ($j = 0,1,2,3$) are assumed to be exponentially distributed. This system is susceptible under first order differential difference equation to formulate the expression of availability, mean time to failure (MTTF) and profit. The service reliability of the ISP and its impact on clients are thoroughly investigated. These effects however, vary depending on the failure and repair rates. This study will be useful to system engineers for service quality dimensions, as well as designers, plant management, developers, and maintenance personnel in the appropriate design and analysis of maintenance policies or processes in the assessment of system performance and safety in general during and after the burn-in period.

Keywords: Availability; Clients; Internet service provider (ISP); Profit and reliability.

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A Hybrid Cubic B-Spline Galerkin Technique for Solving the Nonlinear Time Fractional Klein-Gordon Equation

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Abstract

This research presents a high-accuracy numerical scheme based on the finite element method to solve the Time Fractional Klein-Gordon Equation (TFKGE). This model is crucial for describing fractional-order scalar fields and non-local wave dynamics in quantum field theory and condensed matter physics. The spatial discretization is achieved using the Cubic B-spline Galerkin method. This choice leverages the superior approximation properties, compact support, and smoothness inherent to cubic B-splines, which are utilized as robust basis functions over the computational domain. A formal coordinate transformation is implemented to establish the necessary correspondence between the global finite element mesh and the local basis function support.

The fractional temporal dynamics are modeled using the Caputo fractional derivative, specifically chosen for its compatibility with standard initial conditions in physical systems. Time discretization employs a hybrid approach, the fractional derivative is approximated via a dedicated standard finite difference scheme, while the unknown field functions are integrated using the Crank-Nicolson method. A rigorous theoretical stability analysis of the resulting full discretization scheme confirms its unconditional stability, guaranteeing reliable computation across various time steps. The proposed method is validated through simulations of several benchmark TFKGE problems. Comparative results against analytical solutions and existing literature confirm the scheme's high accuracy, efficiency, and convergence rate for modeling complex fractional-order wave phenomena.

Keywords: Time Fractional Klein-Gordon Equation (TFKGE); Cubic B-spline; Galerkin finite element method.

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Comments on an Open Problem on Commutativity of Factor Rings

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Abstract

In this study we discuss an open problem given in (M. Zerra, K. Bouchannafa and L. Oukhtite, Georgian Mathematical Journal, vol. 32, no. 1, 2025, pp. 175-182). We give affirmative answer to some particular cases of it.

Keywords: Derivation; Semiprime ideal; Factor ring.

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On Derivations Satisfying Some P-valued Identities in Rings

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Abstract

Let R be an associative ring with center $Z(R)$. In this note, we first extend some recent results on generalized derivations acting on prime ideals and then address some gaps on $*$ -centralizing derivations.

Keywords: Prime ring; Prime ideal; Derivation; Involution; Commutativity.

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Sensor-Based Side-Channel Attack Detection Using Text Inference and Image Inference

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Abstract

Side channel attacks are a type of attack on cryptographic systems that exploit information leaked by the physical implementation of the system, rather than by breaking the mathematical algorithms or cryptographic keys. Some common side channel attacks are Power analysis attacks, Electromagnetic analysis attacks, Acoustic analysis attacks, Timing analysis attacks. Smartphones have become an integral part of our daily lives and are used for a variety of purposes. Smartphones have revolutionized the way we communicate, access information, and stay connected with the world around us. Due to excessive dependency on smartphones, they are particularly vulnerable to side channel attacks because they contain a lot of sensitive data, including personal and financial information, and they are often used for secure transactions, such as mobile payments. Some side-channel attacks focus just on the numeric keys for extracting sensitive information like Credit/Debit Card numbers, ATM PINs, Passwords etc. Some focus on tracking user activity and more. Modern smartphones come equipped with a variety of sensors that allow them to detect and respond to changes in their environment. Some of the most common sensors found in smartphones include: Accelerometer, Gyroscope, Magnetometer, Proximity sensor, Fingerprint sensor. Using these sensors, a lot of sensitive information can be leaked. Thus, this arises a huge privacy issue using the smartphones.

We propose GammaLogger, an application that highlights the issue of leaking smartphone users' privacy by emulating the 'side-channel attack using smartphone hardware sensors (accelerometer, magnetometer, and gyroscope) and inferring images using Computer Vision. GammaLogger will infer the typed text on a smartphone keyboard using Neural Network and further enhancing the output using Language Modeling. The application will also infer the images user sees and tries to caption them in textual form, maintain the log of it and send to the destination email whenever smartphone is connected with the Wi-Fi.

Keywords: Side-Channel attacks; Smartphone sensor leakage; Privacy inference with neural networks.

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Numerical Method for Solving Nonlinear Hyperbolic Equation with Unknown Inverse Coefficient under Periodic Constraints

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Abstract

This paper investigates the inverse problem of determining unknown time-dependent coefficients in a one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions. The Finite Difference Method (FDM) together with the Gauss–Seidel iteration is used for numerical computation. Two implicit finite difference schemes, the fully implicit and Crank–Nicolson methods, are applied. A numerical example illustrates the effectiveness of the proposed method. Results show that while both schemes align well with experimental data, the implicit scheme provides higher accuracy with lower absolute and relative errors.

Keywords: Inverse problem; Nonlinear hyperbolic equation; Finite difference method.

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Numerical Investigation of an Inverse Coefficient Problem in a Nonlinear Hyperbolic Equation

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Abstract

In this study, an inverse coefficient problem for a one-dimensional nonlinear hyperbolic equation with periodic boundary conditions is investigated. The analytical solution is derived using the Fourier method, while the numerical solution is obtained through an implicit finite difference scheme. A comparison of the analytical and numerical results demonstrates that the estimated inverse coefficient and the corresponding v values exhibit excellent agreement, indicating the accuracy and reliability of the proposed approach.

Keywords: Inverse coefficient problem; Nonlinear hyperbolic equation; Finite difference method.

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Effect of Ring Support on Bi-Layered Fgm Cylindrical Shell

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Abstract

This abstract presents a comprehensive study of effect of ring support on bi-layered FGM cylindrical shell. In this work, the effect of ring support is analyzed on bi-layered FGM cylindrical shell. The bi-layered cylindrical shell are composed of two independent materials. These materials are considered nickel and stainless steel. The characteristics of materials are observed by the volume fraction power law. The fundamental frequencies of cylindrical shell are analyzed under the simply supported end boundary condition. The curvature and strain displacement relations are attained from sander's shell theory. The shell fundamental frequency equations are derived by using the Rayleigh Ritz.

Keywords: Ring support; Sander's Shell theory; Rayleigh-Ritz method; Simply supported.

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Existence of Solutions for Random System of Functional Differential Equations

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Abstract

Our results are used to prove the existence, uniqueness and compactness of solutions for systems of random semilinear functional differential equations with initial and boundary conditions. We assume that the linear part generates a strongly continuous semigroup on a general Banach space. Finally, some examples are given to illustrate the results.

In this paper, we give some existence results for functional differential equations with delay and random effects, we study the following systems

$$\begin{cases} x'(t, \omega) = A_1(\omega)x(t, \omega) + f(t, x_t(\cdot, \omega), y_t(\cdot, \omega), \omega), & t \in J := [0, T] \\ y'(t, \omega) = A_2(\omega)x(t, \omega) + g(t, x_t(\cdot, \omega), y_t(\cdot, \omega), \omega), & t \in J := [0, T] \\ x(\theta, \omega) = \varphi(\theta, \omega), & \theta \in [-r, 0] \\ y(\theta, \omega) = \Psi(\theta, \omega), & \theta \in [-r, 0] \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $f, g : J \times C([-r, 0] \times \Omega, X) \times C([-r, 0] \times \Omega, X) \times \Omega \rightarrow X$, (Ω, \mathcal{A}) is a measurable space, $A_i : \Omega \times X \rightarrow X$, $i = 1, 2$ are random operators, φ, Ψ are two random maps and X is a separable Banach space.

This paper is organized as follows: In Section 1, we introduce the material needed in this paper such as generalized metric space, some fixed point theorems. In Section 2, we shall use a random version of the Perov type theorem for the study of problems for random functional differential equations. In Section 3, we present an illustrative and comparative example.

Keywords: Mild solutions; Random variable; Differential equations; Fixed point.

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Solution of Fractional Derivative Homogeneous and Non-Homogeneous Parabolic Problems using the Fourier Method

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Abstract

In this study, fractional derivative homogeneous and non-homogeneous parabolic problems are investigated under periodic boundary conditions. Analytical solutions are obtained using the Fourier method. The results demonstrate the effectiveness of this method in solving fractional parabolic problems.

Keywords: Fractional derivative; Parabolic problems; Fourier method.

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Solution of Differential Equations related to Markov Processes

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Abstract

This work studies the relationship between differential equations and Markov processes, focusing on the characterization and solution of evolution equations associated with stochastic dynamics. In particular, we consider differential equations governing the transition probabilities and expectations of Markov processes, such as the Kolmogorov forward (Fokker–Planck) and backward equations. Analytical and probabilistic techniques are employed to establish existence, uniqueness, and regularity of solutions under suitable conditions on the generator of the process. Several examples, including diffusion and jump processes, illustrate how these equations describe the temporal evolution of probability distributions and expectations. The results highlight the deep connection between stochastic analysis and partial differential equations in modeling random phenomena

Keywords: Stochastic differential equations; Markov processes.

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Optimization and Sensitivity Analysis of Non-Isothermal Fluid Flow for Constrained Roll Coating System: A Comparative Investigation

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Abstract

This article offers a comprehensive theoretical and numerical analysis of non-isothermal fluid flow, utilizing the power law model, across the tiny gap between a rotating roll and a stationary wall. The governing energy and momentum equations are formulated in non-dimensional form via suitable transformations and are reduced via lubrication theory. We derive approximate analytical solutions for temperature, velocity profile, pressure gradient, and pressure distribution using perturbation techniques, while numerical solutions are obtained by Dsolve (utilizing the Midrich method) and the finite difference strategy. Key engineering quantities are determined based on analytical solutions, including coating thickness, roll separation forces, Nusselt number streamlines, and power input necessary for operating the roll under coating conditions, taking into account the system's kinematics and geometric features. Additionally, we utilize the Response surface method to analyze the power law model and evaluate its suitability for optimization. Sensitivity analysis is conducted to quantify the impacts of the Weissenberger number and the gravity parameter on roll splitting force, coating thickness, and power input. The significant coefficients of determination validate the precision of the model. The robustness of our findings is further evidenced by a significant correlation between the perturbation and numerical methods, as well as a positive comparison with previous studies. This analysis offers valuable insights aimed at improving the efficiency of industrial coating processes and prolonging the lifespan of substrates.

Keywords: Non-Newtonian fluid; Roll coating process; Finite difference approximation; Power law model; Sensitivity analysis; Lubrication theory.

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Error Estimation for Adam Bashforth Scheme of High-Index Saddle Dynamics

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Abstract

High-index saddle dynamics offers an efficient method for calculating saddle points of any index and building the solution landscape effectively. In this paper, we use the typical Adam Bashforth multi-step method for numerical discretization of the high-index saddle dynamics. We prove error estimates for second order Adam Bashforth multi-step discretization of high-index saddle dynamics with respect to the time step size, which is not addressed in the literature. During convergence order proof process, we employ mathematical induction to demonstrate the boundedness of the characteristic vectors obtained at each step and to demonstrate the error estimates for the discretization of high-index saddle dynamics by Adam Bashforth with respect to the time step size. At the Numerical experiments are rigorously performed to validate the theoretical reliability of the proposed schemes, involving varied parameters and conditions to assess their robustness and accuracy.

Keywords: Saddle point; Saddle dynamic; Solution landscape; Adam Bashforth method; Error estimates.

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Electromagnetic Influence on Wave Dynamics in the (3+1)-Dimensional Modified KdV–Zakharov–Kuznetsov Framework

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Abstract

This study focuses on understanding wave propagation in dispersive and nonlinear media by analyzing the dynamic behavior of the modified KdV-Zakharov-Kuznetsov (mKdV-ZK) equation. Building on the extensively researched KdV-ZK equation, we examine solitary wave solutions of the (3+1)-dimensional mKdV-ZK equation using the extended modified Sardar sub-equation method. As a result, a diverse array of novel soliton solutions are obtained, including multi-peak solitons, kink and anti-kink waves, dark and bright solitons, and breather waves. These analytical solutions are derived in terms of key physical quantities such as electrostatic field potential, quantum statistical pressure, electric fields, and magnetic fields. Graphical representations are provided to illustrate the distinct dynamical features of the obtained wave solutions, highlighting their relevance to plasma physics, nonlinear optics, and electromagnetic wave propagation. The results confirm that the extended modified Sardar sub-equation method is an efficient and versatile tool for solving higher-dimensional nonlinear partial differential equations, with broad applicability to nonlinear wave systems in applied mathematics and physical sciences.

Keywords: Modified KdV-ZK equation; Extended modified Sardar sub-equation method; Bright soliton; Kink and anti-kink type waves; Electric and magnetic fields; Electrostatic potential.

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Advanced Fuzzy Aggregation Operators for Multi-Criteria Decision-Making in Circular Intuitionistic Systems

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Abstract

In this research, a new fuzzy modeling framework is proposed to better capture uncertainty and interdependence in multi-criteria decision-making environments. The approach employs a circular intuitionistic structure that simultaneously considers degrees of membership, non-membership, and their geometric relationship through a radius parameter. To aggregate this information effectively, a class of nonlinear combination operators constructed on Einstein-type principles is developed, enabling more adaptive and expressive fusion of evaluation data than traditional aggregation schemes. The operators are further extended into weighted arithmetic and geometric forms to ensure coherent and interpretable decision outcomes. Their theoretical soundness is established through key mathematical properties, and the framework's performance is illustrated using an case study evaluation. The comparative results demonstrate stable and meaningful rankings, highlighting the method's potential as a versatile tool for decision-making under uncertainty.

Keywords: MCDM; Aggregation operators; TOPSIS.

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Turning Apple Enzymes into Innovation: A Kyrgyz-Slovak Approach to Sustainable Biotechnology

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Abstract

The research aims to transform natural biodiversity into practical biotechnological innovation through the extraction and application of polyphenol oxidase (PPO) enzymes derived from apple cultivars native to Kyrgyzstan and Slovakia. These enzymes exhibit strong catalytic activity in phenolic compound oxidation, making them valuable for sustainable industrial use.

The developed product utilizes purified PPO as a biocatalyst with potential applications in food preservation, biosensor development, and eco-friendly oxidation systems. Comparative analysis of Kyrgyz and Slovak apple PPOs revealed distinct enzymatic stability, thermal tolerance, and substrate specificity properties that can be optimized for industrial biotechnology.

The innovation focuses on enzyme-based technology for natural product stabilization, emphasizing low-cost production, renewable sourcing, and environmental sustainability. This biotechnological approach bridges biodiversity and applied science by combining genetic and biochemical characterization with practical engineering design. By merging Kyrgyz biodiversity and Slovak biotechnological expertise, this project introduces a cross-national model for green innovation. The resulting PPO-based bio-product represents a step toward eco-conscious enzyme technologies, supporting the growing global demand for sustainable and circular bioeconomy solutions.

Keywords: Polyphenol oxidase; Enzyme purification; Sustainable biotechnology.

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Utilization of Liquorice Root and Fennel Seed Based Herbal Teamix for the Relief of Asthma

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Abstract

Lifestyle modification and poor nutrition have led to a major shift in eating patterns. Herbal foods have gained extensive consideration because of the presence of abundant phytonutrients in them. Among the beverage products, Tea is mostly liked by individuals from different age group. However, their nutritional quality can further be improved by incorporating healthy ingredients like liquorice root and fennel seed powder. Liquorice root has functional and therapeutic potential to treat asthma due to the presence of bioactive components like Glycyrrhizin. The present project has been designed to find out quality characteristics of herbal teamix incorporated with liquorice root and fennel seed powder. For the purpose, liquorice root and fennel seed powder were prepared and evaluated for mineral, total phenolic content, total flavonoid, antioxidant analysis, and bioactive component. The results of the mineral content of liquorice root and fennel seed powder showed that it holds (1203mg) calcium, (1737mg) potassium, (372mg) magnesium. Liquorice root possessed total phenolic content (873mg GAE/100g) and total flavonoid content (270mg RE/100g). Antioxidant (DPPH) value was (70%), and bioactive compound (31.7g) and Fennel seed possess total phenolic content (13.47mg GAE/100g) and total flavonoid content (0.04mg RE/100g). Antioxidant (DPPH) value was (78%). Liquorice root powder was mixed with fennel seed powder in different combinations. All formulations were converted into herbal teamix followed by their compositional and phytochemical analysis. The demonstration of mineral analysis of all treatments of herbal teamix from T₀ to T₅ showed ranges of calcium (118.17 to 489.98mg), potassium (40.45 to 680.99mg), magnesium (1.94 to 157.31mg) mg/100g respectively. The TPC results illustrated that the highest content (853.05mg) was found in T₀, and lowest (516.73mg) in T₅. The highest TFC (268.24mg) was also present in T₀. Antioxidant activity ranged from (68.46mg) for T₀ to (72.27)mg for T₅. The product was also assessed for color. With the decrease in the liquorice powder, color of herbal teamix was also decreased. Afterwards, sensory acceptability of the product was judged for different attributes like color, taste, aroma, mouthfeel, and overall acceptability. Based on composition and sensory analysis, herbal teamix containing 70% liquorice root powder and 30 of fennel seed powder (T₄) was preferred as best treatment. From the results it was clear that there was a need to use underrated but versatile herbs like liquorice root and fennel seeds to develop value added products with high nutritional value.

Keywords: Liquorice root; Fennel seed; Asthma.

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Exploring the Therapeutic Effect of *Ficus benghalensis* Fruit Powder against Diabetes in Albino Rats

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Abstract

Diabetes is a chronic metabolic disease. International diabetic federation (IDF) reported that approximately about 8 million people died of diabetes in 2021. This highlights the widespread nature of diabetes, a prevalent non-communicable disease characterized by high blood glucose level. Interestingly, within the realm of traditional medicine particularly ayurveda, the *Ficus benghalensis* (commonly known as Banyan fruit) boasts a long history of medicinal application primarily the bark, fruit and aerial roots of this plant are used to treat diabetes. Banyan fruit contains many bioactive compounds such as glycosides and polyphenols that help the body in the regulation of diabetes. In this study, the fruit was dried by different methods such as hot air method, microwave oven drying, and sun drying. The dried fruit was stored for further usage. The effect of drying treatment on the *Ficus benghalensis* fruit was assessed through proximate analysis, phytochemical profile, total saponin contents, and vitamin C contents present in it. The anti-diabetic potential of the fruit powder was assessed in albino rats. The sample dried through the sun drying showed the best results of moisture, fat, protein, and other proximate values. The value of total phenolic contents (TPC) and antioxidant capacity (DPPH) was highest in the microwave oven dried, while total flavonoid contents (TFC) were highest in the hot air oven dried sample. The amount of vitamin C contents was also highest in microwave oven dried sample. Then the anti-diabetic effect of the powder at 500mg/kg body showed the best results while the 250mg/kg and 350mg/kg showed less effect against diabetes.

Keywords: Banyan fruit; Diabetes; Ayurveda; Nutraceuticals.

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Identification of Metabolic Pathways Linked to the Antibacterial Activity of trans-13-Octadecanoic Acid Found in Schistocerca Gregaria Oil

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Abstract

With the growing threat of antimicrobial resistance (AMR), natural compounds such as insect-derived fatty acids offer promising alternatives. In this study, we employed bioinformatic tools to explore the potential antibacterial mechanisms of trans-13-octadecanoic acid against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. This bioactive lipid compound was identified in *Schistocerca gregaria* oil through GC-MS analysis, and its structure was further examined using cheminformatics databases. Functional enrichment and metabolic pathway analyses were conducted using KEGG, HMDB platforms. Our findings suggest that trans-13-octadecanoic acid may exert antibacterial effects by targeting bacterial membrane biosynthesis, disrupting oxidative phosphorylation, and modulating fatty acid metabolism. These insights provide a computational basis for experimental validation of insect-derived lipids as novel antimicrobial agents.

Keywords: Antibacterial activity and antimicrobial resistance; Bioinformatics and metabolic pathways; *Schistocerca gregaria* oil and trans-13-octadecanoic acid.

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Kocaeli University, Faculty of Arts and Sciences
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Phenotype-Stratified Staphylococcus Aureus and MRSA Colonization in Persistent Allergic Rhinitis: A Precision Medicine Risk Model

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Abstract

Colonization by methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA) in individuals with allergic rhinitis is poorly understood despite the bacterium's potent exacerbation of Type 2 airway inflammation. Prior studies have not yet examined MRSA patterns across clinical phenotypes or established phenotype-specific risk models.

This research sought to determine phenotype-level MRSA carriage and resistance characteristics and to develop a clinically validated risk-stratification approach for persistent allergic rhinitis.

A prospective cohort of 136 patients with persistent allergic rhinitis was recruited at Hospital Serdang, Malaysia (March 2024–April 2025). Participants were categorized by latent class analysis into mild (VAS ≤ 3 , monosensitized), moderate (VAS 4–5, polysensitized to 3–5 allergens), or severe (VAS ≥ 5 , polysensitized to \geq five allergens with comorbid asthma/eczema). Nasal swabs were analyzed with nuc PCR for *S. aureus*, mecA PCR for MRSA, and screening for hla virulence gene. Resistance patterns were measured, while multivariable logistic regression identified predictors of colonization. Model validity was assessed with ROC-AUC, Hosmer-Lemeshow statistics, and Nagelkerke R².

S. aureus colonization followed a phenotype-dependent increase: mild 15.0%, moderate 36.1%, and severe 57.5%. Severe cases showed tenfold higher colonization odds than mild cases. MRSA carriage was also higher in the severe (52.9%) than in the mild (23.5%) group. Nearly all isolates expressed the hla gene. Independent risk factors included severe phenotype, multisensitization, and asthma comorbidity. The risk model yielded an AUC of 0.782. Significant number of MRSA isolates were multidrug resistant but remained sensitive to mupirocin and fusidic acid.

Clinical phenotypes are strong predictors of MRSA colonization risk in persistent allergic rhinitis. The validated model supports targeted screening and decolonization for precision antimicrobial stewardship.

Keywords: Persistent allergic rhinitis; MRSA; Nasal carriage; Phenotypic risk; Multidrug resistance; Staphylococcus aureus.

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Subfossil Chironomids from two Neighbouring, Size-differing Lakes in the Eastern Carpathians, Romania

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Abstract

Subfossil chironomid remains were examined from short sediment sequences collected from two neighbouring alpine lakes in the Maramures Mountains, Eastern Carpathians, Romania to assess and compare their past environmental changes. Lake Vinderel with a 0.9 ha area and 5.5 m maximum depth represents the largest lake in the region, whereas the Lake Livia with a 0.06 ha area and 3.5 m maximum depth is rather a small pond situated nearby. In this study, 34 cm long sediment sequences from lake Vinderel and 28 cm long sediment sequences from Livia were analysed.

Both lakes yielded low taxonomic richness with 11 taxa for each lake. The assemblages of both lakes were dominated by *Procladius* sp., *Chironomus anthracinus*-type and *Tanytarsus lugens*-type. In contrast, *Endochironomus impar*-type appeared solely in lake Livia which suggesting low pH periods. Moreover, littoral taxa such as *Dicrotendipes nervosus*-type and *Microtendipes pedellus*-type were observed only in Lake Vinderel, whereas semi-terrestrial *Limnophyes-Paralimnophyes* was exclusive to Lake Livia.

Keywords: Eastern Carpathians; Romania; Subfossil chironomids; Lake Vinderel; Lake Livia.

This study was supported by the project APVV-20-0358.

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Influence of Electromagnetic Induction Heating (EIH) Parameters on Thermal Gradient Formation in 7075 Aluminum Alloys

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Abstract

This abstract presents a comprehensive study of the influence of EIH parameters such as power input, operating frequency, air-gap length, workpiece geometry, and material properties on thermal gradient formation in 7075 aluminum alloy. Experimental results reveal that increasing the power level produces fast heating with more pronounced thermal gradients. When the operating frequency was increased from 10 kHz to 40 kHz, heating rates increased with localized heating at the center region of the workpiece. The geometry of the workpiece also affects the induction heating process; specimens with rectangular geometry reached a lower peak temperature with lower thermal gradients as compared to arc edge specimens. However, the distance between the coil and the workpiece shows an inverse relationship with peak temperatures. A coupled electromagnetic simulation model was established using COMSOL Multiphysics verified these infrared measurements. These findings on non-uniform heating patterns, pave the way for advanced EIH equipment for warm forming of AA7075 in aerospace and automotive industries.

Keywords: Electromagnetic induction heating; Thermal gradient; Aluminum alloys.

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Hermite-Hadamard-Mercer Type Inequalities for Twice Differentiable Convex Involving Riemann-Liouville Fractional Integrals

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Abstract

In this study, authors use Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals to get several new inequalities of Hermite-Hadamard-Mercer type. We establish some trapezoid and midpoint type inequalities for functions whose twice derivatives in absolute value are convex involving Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals. The results of the paper are extensions and refinements of Hermite-Hadamard and Hermite-Hadamard-Mercer type inequalities. We discuss special cases of our main results and give new inequalities of the Hermite-Hadamard and Hermite-Hadamard-Mercer type. These results are accompanied by further remarks and observations. Next, we see the efficiency of our inequalities via some applications on special means. Lastly, a couple of examples through graphical visualizations are provided to illustrate the key findings of our research.

Keywords: Hermite-Hadamard inequality; Jensen Mercer inequality; Hermite-Hadamard Mercer inequality; Riemann-Liouville fractional integrals; Convex function.

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Comparative Evaluation of PLGA Nanoparticle Formulations for Gene Delivery Applications

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Abstract

To achieve effective gene therapy, it is essential to utilize nanoparticles that can safeguard nucleic acids (such as miRNA and siRNA), enhance cellular uptake and targeting efficiency, facilitate endosomal escape, and promote intracellular targeting.

PLGA has been extensively studied as a vehicle for gene delivery due to its biodegradability, biocompatibility, low toxicity, controlled and sustained release properties, and its safety for administration, as recognized by the US FDA (Food and Drug Administration).

In this research, we compared two PLGA formulations by preparing and analyzing them based on size, surface charge, and stability. The physicochemical characterization demonstrated formulation-dependent differences in nanoparticle size, polydispersity, and zeta potential. To measure the uptake of nucleic acids in the cancer cell line, Cy3-labeled versions were utilized.

In summary, these findings indicate that varying PLGA formulations play a critical role in influencing nanoparticle size and zeta potential, thereby impacting gene delivery efficacy and facilitating intracellular delivery.

Keywords: Gene delivery; PLGA; Cancer.

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Mechanisms of Resistance to Immune Checkpoint Inhibitors: Why Immunotherapy Works in Only a Minority of Patients

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Abstract

Immune checkpoint inhibitors (ICIs) targeting PD-1/PD-L1 and CTLA-4 have transformed oncology, yet their real-world impact remains limited: immunotherapy is currently applicable to only about 20% of all cancer types, and among patients treated with PD-1/PD-L1 inhibitors, durable responses occur in only 15–20%. Resistance to checkpoint blockade arises from a multifaceted inter play between tumor-intrinsic genetic alterations, an immunosuppressive tumor microenvironment, and host-related determinants. Loss of antigen presentation, β 2-microglobulin mutations, impaired interferon- γ signaling, and activation of oncogenic pathways such as PI3K/AKT, STK11/LKB1, and KEAP1 diminish T-cell recognition and weaken antitumor immunity. Within the tumor microenvironment, regulatory T cells, myeloid-derived suppressor cells, tumor-associated macrophages, and cancer-associated fibroblasts create structural and metabolic barriers that limit T-cell infiltration, effector function, and metabolic fitness. Host factors—including gut microbiota composition, germline immune variants, HLA repertoire, and systemic inflammatory state—further influence therapeutic outcomes and shape both primary and acquired resistance. Sensitivity to ICIs varies widely across tumors: triple-negative breast cancer shows moderate benefit when combined with chemotherapy, whereas pancreatic duct adenocarcinoma and glioblastoma remain profoundly resistant due to dense stromal architecture and highly suppressive immune landscapes. Predictive biomarkers such as PD-L1 expression, tumor mutational burden, microsatellite instability, and interferon-related gene signatures provide partial guidance for patient selection but lack universal accuracy. Current strategies to overcome resistance include combination regimens with chemotherapy, radiotherapy, PARP and VEGF inhibitors, epigenetic modulators, and dual or multi-checkpoint blockade targeting emerging pathways such as LAG-3, TIGIT, and TIM-3. Future advances are expected from personalized neoantigen-based vaccines, engineered T-cell therapies, microbiome modulation, and multi-omic/AI-integrated platforms aimed at producing more precise and durable immunotherapeutic responses.

Keywords: Immunotherapy; Immune checkpoint inhibitors; PD-1/PD-L1; CTLA-4; Resistance mechanisms.

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Self-Assembled Graphene Oxide Membrane for Water Purifications

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Abstract

This abstract presents a comprehensive study of Graphene Oxide Membrane for Water Purifications. We investigate the fundamental properties of Graphene and its derivatives and establish new experimental results that extend previous work in the field. Our main contributions include: (1) the development of a novel filtration mechanism to purify polluted water

The accelerating growth of global population and industrialization has intensified environmental pollution, with water contamination emerging as a critical threat to human health. Addressing the escalating shortage of freshwater requires advanced purification technologies, among which nanomaterial-based filtration systems have shown exceptional promise. Graphene and its derivatives offer unique advantages-including outstanding mechanical strength, high charge mobility, and precisely defined nano-channels that permit the transport of single-layer water molecules—along with strong interactions with both polar and non-polar solvents. In the present work, graphene oxide (GO) was synthesized using the improved Hummer's method and employed to fabricate nano-channel filtration membranes through a controlled self-assembly process. The resulting membranes, approximately 30 μm in thickness and 4 cm in diameter, feature interlayer nano-channels of ~ 4.2 Å. These channels effectively block the passage of atoms, ions, and molecules with hydrated radii exceeding the channel dimensions, thereby enabling selective desalination. Total dissolved solids (TDS) analysis demonstrated a substantial reduction in impurities, confirming the efficacy of GO-based membranes as viable nano-filtration media for water purification.

Keywords: Self-assembly; Nano-channel membranes; Graphene oxide; Desalination; Permeation; Nano-pore size.

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A New Study on Hermite-Hadamard Inequalities for Specific Convexity Classes and Application

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Abstract

This paper presents a comprehensive analysis of (s,m)-exponential-type functions which are convex, emphasizing their foundational algebraic properties. Building upon this framework, we derive class of latest results of Hermite-Hadamard-type inequalities by using Caputo-Fabrizio fractional integral operator. This study introduces improved integral inequalities for functions exhibiting (s,m)-exponential convexity in their powered absolute derivatives. The efficacy of these results is demonstrated through refined estimations of special means and tighter error bounds in trapezoidal and midpoint integration schemes.

Keywords: Exponential convexity; Power-mean inequality; Holder's inequality.

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Fractional Simpson-Like Inequalities for Thrice Differentiable Functions

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Abstract

In this investigation, new fractional Simpson-like inequalities for thrice differentiable functions are established by using bounded functions. Moreover, with the aid of Lipschitzian functions, some new fractional Simpson-like inequalities for thrice differentiable functions are also obtained. In addition, by considering specific parameter values, some known results are recovered as special cases of the main theorems, particularly those corresponding to the Riemann–Liouville fractional integral operator.

Keywords: Simpson-type inequality; Bounded functions; Lipschitzian functions.

POSTER PRESENTATIONS

2nd KOCAELİ SCIENCE CONGRESS (KOSC-2025)

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NGS-Based Analysis of Mutations in Colorectal Cancer Patients

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Abstract

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is a heterogeneous malignancy arising from the accumulation of genetic and epigenetic alterations in key molecular pathways, primarily chromosomal instability (CIN), microsatellite instability (MSI), and CpG island methylator phenotype (CIMP). Despite advances in screening and treatment, CRC remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality world wide. The identification of recurrent gene mutations has provided significant insight into the mechanisms driving tumor initiation and progression.

This study aimed to investigate the molecular and genetic alterations underlying CRC by analyzing pathogenic variants in key oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes through next-generation sequencing (NGS).

Tumor samples from 27 colorectal cancer patients (17 males, 10 females) at Kocaeli University Hospital were analyzed using an NGS panel targeting key oncogenes and tumor suppressor genes to identify clinically relevant pathogenic variants.

The most frequently observed mutations were TP53 (19/27), KRAS (11/27), and ERBB2 (6/27). Other detected mutations included BRAF (4/27), PIK3CA (4/27), EGFR (2/27), AKT1 (1/27), CTNNB1 (1/27), ESR1 (1/27), PDGFRA (1/27), and RAF1 (1/27). No NRAS mutations were detected.

These results show that TP53 and KRAS mutations are predominant, reflecting CIN-driven tumorigenesis, while ERBB2 amplifications suggest potential targets for precision therapy. Overall, the findings highlight the mutational heterogeneity of CRC and the value of NGS-based profiling in guiding personalized diagnosis and treatment.

Keywords: Colorectal cancer; Chromosomal instability; ERBB2; TP53; KRAS; Next-generation sequencing; Molecular profiling.

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Subfossil Chironomids Reveal Past Hydrologic Shift in Lake Lala Mare, Eastern Carpathians

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Abstract

Lala Mare is a high-altitude glacial lake (1800 m a.s.l.) located in the Rodna Mountains of the Eastern Carpathians, Romania. In the present study, subfossil chironomids were analysed from a 20 cm sediment sequence to reconstruct past ecological and environmental conditions. A total of 1863 head capsules, representing 26 taxa, were identified, with overall low taxonomic richness. The assemblages were mainly dominated by *Tanytarsus lugens*-type and *Procladius* sp.

Hierarchical classification analysis revealed two distinct zones: The lower zone was characterized by high abundances of *Tanytarsus lugens*-type, whereas in the upper zone *Procladius* sp. became dominant, by a decline in overall diversity, suggesting enhanced productivity. Cold-adapted taxa associated with flowing water, including *Diamesa*, *Eukiefferiella*, *Tvetenia*, and *Pseudodiamesa branickii*-type, were frequent in the 1st Zone, reflecting a cold inflow. In contrast, rheophilic taxa disappeared in the second zone, reflecting a shift water inflow and hydrological changes.

Keywords: Chironomidae; Eastern Carpathians; Romania; Subfossil chironomids.

The research was supported by the project APVV-20-0358.

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Liraglutide Induces DR5-Mediated Apoptosis and Suppresses Proliferation in Breast Cancer Cells

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Abstract

This study evaluates the anticancer potential of the GLP-1 receptor agonist liraglutide in estrogen-positive (MCF-7) and estrogen-negative (MDA-MB-231) breast cancer cell lines, focusing on its interaction with the DR5 (Death Receptor 5) apoptotic pathway. Cell viability analysis demonstrated that liraglutide significantly reduced proliferation after 72 hours of treatment, yielding IC₅₀ values of 3400 nM for MDA-MB-231 and 4800 nM for MCF-7 cells. Flow cytometric assessment revealed a marked increase in early and late apoptotic populations, together with elevated DR5 expression following treatment. Protein expression analysis confirmed the upregulation of DR5 and p53, supporting the activation of apoptotic signaling mechanisms. Collectively, these findings demonstrate that liraglutide inhibits breast cancer cell growth and induces apoptosis through DR5-dependent signaling, suggesting its potential as a promising therapeutic candidate for breast cancer treatment. Further preclinical validation is warranted to clarify its efficacy and safety in translational applications.

Keywords: Liraglutide; Apoptosis; DR5 signaling; Breast cancer.

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Spin-Polarized Two-dimensional Electron Gas in LaTiO₃/EuTiO₃/SrTiO₃ Heterostructure

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Abstract

Complex oxide interfaces have become a cornerstone in the pursuit of quantum materials, enabling the emergence of exotic electronic and magnetic phases that are foundational for future spintronic and quantum technologies. In this project, I will grow LTO/ETO/STO films using Pulsed Laser Deposition (PLD) to explore the induction of a spin polarized two-dimensional electron gas (2DEG) by introducing magnetic ETO layer having thickness 1 μ c. Utilizing strain engineering and temperature modulation, this project aims to fine-tune the heterostructure's magnetic and electronic properties. The findings provide valuable insights into orbital hybridization and magnetic control, advancing the design of next-generation devices for efficient data processing in quantum and spintronic applications.

Keywords: Spin-Polarized 2DEG; Complex oxide interfaces; Strain-engineered heterostructures.